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**RESHAPING
BANKING AND STOPPING
MONEY LAUNDERING
AT THE AGE OF
AI MANAGED QUALITY**

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In the quarterly journal, articles of ICAB Members, Members from other Accountancy bodies, Academics and Business Leaders from home and abroad are published.

In half yearly journal, articles focus on macro-economy of the country are published.

The monthly news bulletin publishes different ICAB events of the month. This bulletin acts as an information hub for the Members to keep up-to-date about ICAB and its activities in addition to these publications, ICAB also publishes books, monographs, booklets and Students' Study Manuals regularly.

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“Over the years, the country's economy stumbled from time to time. So, there should be a holistic approach we require to boost-up the economy and bring about astringent reforms in the governance structure.”

Md. Shahadat Hossain FCA
Chairman - Editorial Board and
Past President & Council
Member - ICAB

At present, the economy of Bangladesh is sailing through a vintage point of time as transparency, accountability and good governance are gaining their traction in all segments of the society. We all know that a well-developed financial sector might play a key role in defining a path of economic development characterized by sustainable, and long-run economic growth. In order to become a prosperous Nation, the country requires huge investments of physical capital, human capital, technological knowhow the innovation enabled industrial sector, financial sector, business regulation, and therein the gap should be narrowed down.

Over the years, the country's economy stumbled from time to time. So, there should be a holistic approach we require to boost-up the economy and bring about astringent reforms in the governance structure.

In the previous regime, there used to be a huge disruption in the state machineries. Many policies were not implemented even in a decade because politicians turned to businessmen and viceversa and bureaucrats were influenced explicitly by the politicians.

No doubt, we have persistent technical and resource constraints, sometimes re-structuring administrative and economic processes would be quite difficult, but nothing is impossible while we have strong willingness and determination.

To expedite the long term development of the country, robust initiatives are required to ensure transparency, protect consumers' interests and create a competitive market.

We are dreaming of a prosperous country ahead despite the global economic outlook remains challenging, and the growth is expected to moderate across most developing countries in Asia including Bangladesh.

We have an urge of making the Journal more acceptable and pervasive on all intellectual platforms; our team has acquired 'Digital Object Identifier (DOI)' of The Bangladesh Accountant following some rigorous process, which is a persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify various objects, standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), would add a new facet to this publication.

Finally, we would like to appreciate your suggestions, comments and efforts in maintaining a quality journal in the days to come.

President's Desk

“ Pragmatic initiatives are required to improve the ranking of Bangladesh in the ease of doing business index where the financial reporting and the involvement of Chartered Accountants are a precondition to bring more discipline, accountability and transparency in the financial system of Bangladesh.”

Mohammed Forkan Uddin
FCA
President - ICAB

The Bangladesh Accountant' is an endeavor of the Institute to propagate knowledge and experience among the members and the stakeholders. Our Editorial Board and a team of experts are relentlessly working to bring out the descriptive and analytical journal regularly to facilitate our members and other stakeholders to keep them abreast of the phenomenal changes and evolving economic dimension. The articles published in the July-September issue of the Journal mainly focus on current critical issues influencing the accounting profession and the areas of Bangladesh economy. There is no doubt, given the challenges and potentials, our economy is resilient and has huge potential to grow faster. After the change of political landscape of the country in August, a new hope is beaming through as the initiatives are wider taken for reformation in the structural system of corruption in government mechanism. The World Bank (WB) estimates that Bangladesh's GDP growth will be 4% for the fiscal year 2024-2025, which ends in June 2025. This is a significant downgrade from the WB's previous forecast of 5.7%. The WB attributes the downgrade to the political and economic uncertainties that have arisen following recent political turmoil in Bangladesh. However, we see the lights over the clouds and Augean stable agglomeration in our economy and hope that soon the economy will come back in sprit and gain its footing on the back of rebounding in industrial activity, specially RMG production and exports.

In July-August, merchandise exports decreased slightly compared to the same period a year earlier, largely due to a small drop in ready-made garment exports amid country's political instability, slowing global economy and aggressive efforts of peer countries to capture more market share. We need to

focus on export of other items like pharmaceuticals, cement, processed food, leather, telecoms, etc. The initiatives of the Government to diversify export product basket will reduce the dependence on RMG and raise country's export to an expected level.

Pragmatic initiatives are required to improve the ranking of Bangladesh in the ease of doing business index where the financial reporting and the involvement of Chartered Accountants are a precondition to bring more discipline, accountability and transparency in the financial system of Bangladesh. Chartered Accountants are continuously engaging their endeavor to improve the quality of financial reporting so that the interest of investors, Government agencies and consumers are duly protected.

We welcome all stakeholders to join us in this noble initiative and let's work together to build a hunger-free, prosperous and corruption-free Bangladesh.

Thank you.

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Banking Sector on the Edge of a Cliff: Time is Now to Tackle this Anarchy

Mohammad Zahid Hossain FCA

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Introduction

The banking sector is the backbone of the financial system of a country. The role of the banking sector for the economic development of Bangladesh has been pivotal for the past four decades. Today's "industrial revolution" is the result of a pragmatic partnership of the banking sector with private sector entrepreneurs.

The first-generation entrepreneurs with almost "zero capital" were encouraged to go for industrial undertakings obtaining credit lines from commercial banks. During the 1980s, with an objective to boost industrialisation and employment, several private commercial banks were given permission in addition to the then state-owned commercial and specialised banks. With the passage of time, many banks and non-banking financial institutions obtained licences to operate business in Bangladesh. Many of them were required to cater to the increased need of the economy while some decisions were politically motivated. This was acknowledged by Mr Abul Maal Abdul Muhith, the then finance minister of the government led by the Bangladesh Awami League. (Source: bdnews24.com, 24 Jul 2011).

That was the starting point of the Awami League government in establishing indiscipline as well as deregulation in the banking sector through politicising it and today's dicey state of this sector is the

planned consequence of the recently fallen regime.

Sky-rocketing Trend of Bad Loans

During the last 15 years, non-performing loans (NPLs) soared at an unprecedented rate of 713%. Such toxic assets in the banking sector were BDT 224.81 billion when the Awami League formed the government in 2009, while it climbed to BDT 1822.95 billion mark at the end of March 2024. The rate of NPLs was highest ever at 11.11% in the history of Bangladesh. According to industry insiders, the actual rate of NPLs is 3-4 times higher than the declared one. Pressure groups did not allow the lenders to classify the loans according to the Bangladesh Bank's regulatory policy. Many stories of irregularities and undue influences of government high-ups are being unveiled after the student-mass uprising and the resultant ouster of Sheikh Hasina on 05 August 2024. Among 61 banks operating in the country, 63.28% classified loans were concentrated within 10 banks and top five banks' classified loan concentrations were 45.12% (Source: Quarterly Financial Stability report of Bangladesh Bank, September 2023). This is giving an indication of serious lapses of governance prevailing in the banking sector.

Rampant Corruption Backed by High-ups of Past Regime

Sikdar Group issue: After the end of 15 years' autocratic

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regime, the central bank asked Sonali Bank, a state-owned commercial bank, to classify a loan of BDT 1.0 billion disbursed earlier in favour of a large group of company, which was known to be a close ally of the past regime. This loan was appropriate to be classified under bad and loss category while the lender obtained “special approval” from the central bank to classify it as a regular loan. Another private commercial bank (PCB), National Bank Limited, was taken over by Sikdar Group in 2009 under the leadership of Zainul Haque Sikder, the then chairman of the business group. At least BDT 300 billion was siphoned off from the bank under the guise of loans. The

regulators could not take legitimate action against the culprits considering the political identity of the chairman. The Sikder family became desperate and ran wild because nobody was in the country to stop them from perpetrating their wrongdoings. Two directors of Sikder Group (sons of the chairman of the bank) allegedly tried to kill Exim Bank (another PCB) managing director (MD) Mohammad Haider Ali Mia and additional MD Mohammad Firoz Hossain by shooting them for refusing to ‘overprice’ the value of the directors’ mortgaged property to facilitate a loan of BDT 5.0 billion. Instead of punishing these goons, the government gave them a safe exit. These two miscreants left

Dhaka on an air ambulance as ‘patients’ and to stay in safe zone. After the demise of Zainul Haque Sikder in 2021, the Bangladesh Bank investigated a slew of scams of the Sikder family and dissolved the board of directors of National Bank Ltd for the first time. An irreparable loss has, therefore, been recorded in the books of this bank, resulting in a serious challenge for it to pay depositors’ money.

SIBL scam: Another incident of misreporting by Social Islami Bank Ltd (SIBL) came to the fore. SIBL had BDT 95.68 billion in defaulted loans at the end of 2023, whereas it showed only BDT 16.44 billion on its balance sheet based on the clearance from the Bangladesh Bank. This unofficial directive came from the top of the regulator and responsible officers complied with that. The licence of Union Bank Ltd, a shariah-based “problem” bank, was initially issued in favour of HM Ershad, a member of the AL-led grand alliance. The bank was later “purchased” by S Alam Group, and a total of BDT 183.46 billion was approved in favour of 300 companies that existed on paper only. Such loan comprises around 95 per cent of the bank’s total disbursements, which was entitled to be classified according to the central bank’s policy. Despite that, Union Bank did not declare the loans as classified, although it apparently failed to take the money back. They declared less than 4.0% as classified loan, which was nothing but a farce.

Money-eater S Alam issue: Perhaps, the largest “systematic robbery” in the banking sector under the direct patronage of the government took place in Bangladesh. S Alam Group forced the managing director of the Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited at gunpoint to resign from his post after he was taken hostage by members of a government security agency in March 2017 (Source: 31st August 2024, The Daily Star). The objective of the group was to loot that most disciplined and profit-making shariah-based bank of the country. The total disbursed loans of Islami Bank stood at around BDT 1,750 billion of which S Alam Group alone took more than half or BDT 875 billion. Thereafter, this conglomerate “forcefully” took over few more banks, non-banking financial institutions and insurance. However, banking industry

insiders estimate that S Alam Group’s total loans from various banks amount to at least BDT 1.25 trillion, which is around 6.25% of the total loans and advances of the banking system. They were very “innovative” and confident in the embezzlement of bank money and used their political connections to bypass the law. SS Power Plant, a concern of S Alam Group, was licensed to operate a 1320-megawatt coal-based plant and it laundered USD 815 million (BDT 100 billion) through two LCs opened by state-owned Rupali Bank. Although no capital asset reached Bangladesh, fake invoices were used to release the payment in favour of the supplier of China. Without the direct blessings of the central bank, such fraudulent activity cannot remain under the carpet since 2019.

Farmers Bank issue: Former Farmers Bank (later renamed as Padma Bank) fell in a severe capital deficit situation resulting from the fraudulent loan disbursement by the board of directors led by the bank’s chairman Mohiuddin Khan Alamgir. He was the presidium member of the Awami League and a former minister of the government. At the end of December 2017, this volume of the bank’s defaulted loans increased to BDT 7.23 billion. The central bank held Mohiuddin Khan Alamgir and Mahabubul Haque Chisty (the chairman of the executive committee) for their reckless loan management while they did “manage” the law and regulatory body successfully.

Salman Rahman issue: The legendary individual in default culture of Bangladesh’s banking sector is Salman F Rahman, the

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most influential political persona in Bangladesh next to the immediate-past premier. He was the most reliable and trusted adviser of Sheikh Hasina. Salman knew full well of laws and regulations and used his clout over the government system to bend and revise them in his favour. By this means, he rescheduled or restructured his borrowings multiple times setting unprecedented examples. The Bangladesh Bank issued a circular in 2015 stating the rescheduling framework for large borrowers. This circular was issued with an objective to comply with the alleged “wish” of Salman F Rahman. His organisation BEXIMCO’s loan was rescheduled by Sonali Bank under such terms and conditions as Salman thought fit even if they were not in line with the said policy. Companies allegedly related with Salman are having a loan balance of BDT 380.7 billion with different banks. Among them, BDT 230.7

billion was obtained from the state-owned Janata Bank exceeding single borrower exposure limit (Source: The Business Standard, 15th Aug 2024). His loan footprint with other banks is exhibiting clear indication of serious lapses of the law of the land. BEXIMCO issued Sukuk bonds worth BDT 30 billion and used the Bangladesh Securities & Exchange Commission (BSEC) and the Bangladesh Bank to compel top executives of commercial banks to subscribe the bonds of BEXIMCO. Hence, the available fund for general borrowers got squeezed and balanced economic growth is hindered. Despite being a director of a loan-defaulted company, the son of Salman continued to serve as the director in IFIC Bank though it is not legally permissible. This illegal activity was carried out by Salman through his immense political clout. However, after the end of the last regime, the

central bank removed his son from the board of IFIC and reconstituted it.

Conspiracy among Directors of Different Banks

Since there is a restriction of the owners in obtaining loans from their own bank, owners of several banks are entering into “strategic alliance”. They are having collusion to circumvent the law. Shareholder-directors of eight PCBs took loan from each other’s banks. The amount of such loan estimated at BDT 250 billion. Of the banks, six were “occupied” by S Alam Group. These loans were obtained either in the name of directors or their related parties (predominantly their close relatives). In addition to that, the directors of four banks approved loans of BDT 200 billion to the relatives. The owners of these banks contributed BDT 24 billion as capital while they took out loans of BDT 450 billion, which are almost 19 times higher than their capital. According to the directive of the central bank, a director of a PCB can take out a loan not exceeding 50% of his or her capital contribution. It is very likely that a significant amount of BDT 45 billion will turn into bad loans, ultimately throwing the credibility of these banks into question.

Judicial Mockery

The government system was paving a way for the looters to rob money, on the other hand

they took initiative to reduce the rate of NPLs below 8.0% by June 2026 to deceive the general public (Source: BBS News, 4th February 2024). That was nothing but a mockery with the general people of Bangladesh. The largest scamster in the banking sector, S Alam Group, got a verdict from the court not to investigate their money-laundering activities. The Appellate Division on 23 August 2023 ordered the authorities concerned to maintain a status quo until 08 January (12th general election was held on 07 January 2024) on the High Court's order to investigate allegations against S Alam Group's foreign

investments and money transfers without permission from the Bangladesh Bank. (Source: Prothom Alo, 23 August 2023)

Change in Banking Law

The anarchy in the banking sector sponsored by the past AL government was so unashamed that they changed the law regarding the directorship or control of management. With an eye to meeting the "cry for the moon" of the pro-AL bank business leaders, the tenure of a director was extended to 12 years from nine years and necessary amendment was incorporated in

the Bank Companies Act. This underlying reason was to establish and prolong the "influence" of AL-backed directors, while this kind of practice prejudices the interest of the depositors and other stakeholders concerned.

Concluding Remarks

The "black hole" in the banking sector has been so deep that it will require BDT 2.0 trillion to remove the liquidity crisis. There are many "actors and actresses" in the "horror movie" of Hasina's autocratic regime and the stories stated in this article are nothing but "the tip of the iceberg". This significant

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amount of funds was embezzled by four to five “royal” families of the country. This lawlessness culture in the banking system has failed to create confidence in local and foreign stakeholders. As a consequence, on 30 July 2024, S&P Global Ratings lowered its long-term foreign and local currency sovereign credit ratings on Bangladesh to ‘B+’ from ‘BB-’. The drought in foreign direct investment (FDI), growth without employment, continuous reduction in foreign remittances and reserve, and high cost of foreign debt, inter alia, are also directly or indirectly connected with the mayhem in the financial system. The revolutionary July-August student movement compelled the past government to quit power and Hasina to flee to India. The interim government

has formed a task force taking six experts to reform the banking sector. Although discipline in the banking sector cannot be brought overnight through a “magic wand”, at least the process of stopping further damage has been initiated. As part of this move, boards of directors of many weak banks have already been reconstituted to ensure good governance. The goons who robbed the banks in broad daylight must be brought to trial under the law of the land and exemplary punishment be given as deterrents so that wrongdoers can never think to circumvent the law and play around with public money. Most importantly, the laundered money also needs to be repatriated to Bangladesh and injected into the mainstream national economy.

Sources of Information and Acknowledgement

Insert URL addresses and sourced dates here: bdnews24.com, Quarterly Financial Stability Report of Bangladesh Bank, The Daily Star, The Business Standard, BBS News and Prothom Alo

(Facts and figures garnered from the information superhighway have also contributed to making this opinion piece more analytical, insightful and illustrative.)

Money Laundering and Recovery of Siphoned Money International and Bangladesh Context

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The article was reviewed by
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The events of August 5, 2024 have opened a new chapter for Bangladesh, bringing with it a wave of hope for social and economic reforms. The dream of creating more equitable and just society is alive, with people envisioning a future where their rights are upheld and economic independence is secured. However, the path to realizing this dream is not without obstacles. One of the biggest challenges remain stabilizing the economy, which has been weakened by decades of corruption and siphoning of wealth out of the country.

Many believe that if the government launches a determined effort, it is still possible to repatriate stolen assets and set the country on a path to prosperity. The following points will explore from both national and international perspectives.

According to Washington-based Global Financial Integrity, around Tk74,000 crore is laundered annually from Bangladesh. According to Chief Advisors' office information, more than Tk 1 lakh crore has been laundered from Bangladesh. According to Global Financial Integrity Report (2022) we have lost approximately \$8.27 billion annually between 2009 and 2018 due to trade mis-invoicing. In 2018, Swiss National Bank (SNB) reports about \$700 million deposits in Swiss Bank. The sheer scale of money laundering in Bangladesh is

indeed beyond the imagination of most citizens. The case of the then-Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina revealed that a low-level staff member had accumulated Tk 400 crore is a stark reminder of the extent to which corruption has infiltrated various levels of governance and society. Such enormous sums of illicit wealth are difficult to fathom for the average person, and this is just one example among countless others. In Bangladesh there are some agencies that specialize in surveilling any abnormal money transferred. Bangladesh Bank's Financial Intelligence Unit (BFIU), police's Criminal Investigation Department (CID) and the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) were mere spectators and were unable to detect the tip of the iceberg due to political pressure and incompetency in internal structure.

The Process of Recovering Laundered Money

Recovering laundered money that has been moved from one country to another involves a complex legal and financial process. It typically requires cooperation between multiple jurisdictions, law enforcement agencies, and financial institutions. Here is a general outline of the steps involved:

Detection and Investigation

- a. Identifying Suspicious Activity: The process often starts with identifying unusual or suspicious

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- a. the receiving country. This includes bringing charges of money laundering, fraud, or other related crimes.
- b. Civil Asset Recovery: Alongside criminal prosecution, civil lawsuits may be initiated to recover assets by proving that the money was illicitly transferred.

Asset Recovery

- a. Confiscation Orders: Once the laundered money is proven to be illegal, courts may issue confiscation orders to seize the funds in the destination country.
- b. Repatriation of Funds: After confiscation, the laundered money is returned to the originating country through legal agreements and treaties.

Have We Ever Brought Back Laundered Money Ever?

Bangladesh had a success story in 2012, when the Anti-Corruption Commission successfully recovered approximately 20.41 lakh Singapore dollars, equivalent to Tk 13 crore at the time, laundered by BNP Chairperson Khaleda Zia's younger son Arafat Rahman Koko. This is quite a significant proof that if government is believes and remains determined to bring back laundered fund, this is not impossible as long as government who came to power by the revolution have a

transactions through anti-money laundering (AML) protocols, such as those mandated by the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), which may be flagged by banks or financial institutions.

- b. Investigating the money trail: Authorities trace the funds through financial records, including bank accounts, wire transfers, and shell companies. This requires forensic financial investigation to uncover how money was laundered.

International Cooperation

- a. Mutual Legal Assistance Treaties (MLATs): Governments use MLATs to request assistance from

foreign governments in gathering evidence, freezing accounts, or tracing assets.

- b. Involvement of International Organizations: Agencies like Interpol, Europol, and the FATF may assist in cross-border investigations.
- c. Asset Freezing: With cooperation from the foreign country, the laundered money can be temporarily frozen by court orders to prevent further movement.

Legal Action

- a. Prosecution of Offenders: Legal action is initiated against those involved in laundering money, both in the country of origin and

clear mandate for the wellbeing of people.

Challenges in Recovery

Secrecy Jurisdictions and Offshore Accounts: If the funds have been moved to offshore tax havens or countries with strict banking secrecy laws, recovery becomes more difficult.

Legal Barriers: Different legal frameworks, weak enforcement of AML regulations, and corruption in certain jurisdictions can obstruct the recovery process.

Time and Costs: Recovering laundered money is often time-consuming and costly, as it may require lengthy legal battles and significant resources.

International Framework for Anti Money Laundering Activity

United Nations Conventions

- **United Nations Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC, 2005):** UNCAC provides a comprehensive framework for the prevention and recovery of corruption-related assets, including laundered funds. It includes provisions for international cooperation, mutual legal assistance, and asset recovery, making it easier for countries to trace and recover stolen assets.
- **United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC, 2000):** Also known as the Palermo Convention, this treaty aims to combat

organized crime, including money laundering. It encourages countries to criminalize money laundering and promotes international cooperation in law enforcement and judicial matters.

Financial Action Task Force (FATF) Recommendations

- **FATF** is an intergovernmental body that sets international standards to prevent money laundering, terrorist financing, and the financing of weapons of mass destruction. Its 40 Recommendations serve as the global framework for anti-money laundering (AML) efforts, requiring countries to implement laws, regulations, and enforcement mechanisms to detect, prevent, and recover laundered funds.
- **FATF** promotes the use of Mutual Legal Assistance Treaties (MLATs) for cross-border asset recovery and cooperation between countries.

European Union Directives

- **EU Anti-Money Laundering Directives (AMLD):** The EU has issued a series of AML Directives, including the 5th AMLD (2018) and the 6th AMLD (2020). These directives require member states to adopt strict AML regulations, focusing on transparency, cooperation between countries, and

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<p>measures to recover laundered assets.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Investigation Order (EIO): The EIO facilitates the collection of evidence in cross-border criminal cases, including money laundering investigations. It ensures cooperation among EU member states to freeze and confiscate criminal assets. <p>OECD Anti-Bribery Convention (1997)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This convention requires member countries to criminalize the bribery of foreign public officials in international business transactions and mandates 	<p>cooperation in the recovery of bribes and related illicit funds.</p> <p>Egmont Group of Financial Intelligence Units</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Egmont Group is an international organization of Financial Intelligence Units (FIUs) that supports the exchange of financial intelligence to combat money laundering and recover illicit assets. FIUs play a key role in tracking and recovering laundered money across borders. <p>International Asset Recovery Mechanisms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stolen Asset Recovery Initiative (StAR): A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partnership between the World Bank and the UNODC, StAR helps countries recover assets stolen through corruption, focusing on capacity building, international cooperation, and legal reforms. <p>Mutual Legal Assistance Treaties (MLATs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MLATs are bilateral or multilateral agreements between countries to facilitate the exchange of information, evidence, and assistance in criminal matters, including asset recovery. These treaties play a central role in the legal process of tracking and recovering laundered funds.
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Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act (FATCA)

- FATCA is a U.S. law that compels foreign financial institutions to disclose information about accounts held by U.S. taxpayers. It assists in detecting and recovering laundered money tied to tax evasion and related financial crimes.

Together, these laws, treaties, and frameworks provide the legal basis for detecting, freezing, confiscating, and repatriating laundered money across borders. Effective asset recovery often depends on strong international cooperation, adherence to global AML standards, and robust domestic legal systems.

Where Bangladesh Stands on this Framework

After the revolution of 5th

August 2024 hundreds of Money laundering scam has been popping out of the bushes one after another with the bizarre shocks to the nation. The parties involved in this mechanism made these heinous activities as individual and in group perspective in many folds and manner. Biasness tycoons like S. Alam alone smuggled around Tk. 1.13 lakh crore. The beleaguered business behemoth is suspected of conducting illegal hundi operations, involving fraud, forgery, over-invoicing, and under-invoicing to transfer the sum out of the country. Different newspaper already have published the news that to streamline the process industrialist Saiful Alam and his family renounced their Bangladeshi Citizenship and using the siphoned funds purchased movable and immovable assets and operating businesses in Singapore, Malaysia, Cyprus, and various

European countries. Allegation already triggered on the renowned business home Summit Group on illegally laundering money to Singapore. Summit Group founder Muhammed Aziz Khan has become Singapore's 41st richest man with wealth worth \$1.12 billion amassed from different businesses spread from Bangladesh to Singapore, according to US-based Forbes magazine's billionaire list. Root of these incidents are deep and needs high level of investigation. The causes are now visible is just a tip of the iceberg and such nexus is very complicated which is well understood from a documentary recently flooding the web called "The Minister's Millions" by Al Jazeera Investigations which depicts how former MP Saifuzzaman Chowdhury bought hundreds of luxury properties in London, Dubai, and New York, but declared none of them to tax authorities in Bangladesh. All the instances are the example of the loopholes we are keeping at our system for decades to facilitate the perpetrators. We do not have a proper framework and whatever we have is not functioning properly.

The Bangladesh Financial Intelligence Unit (BFIU) is a dedicated public-sector organisation responsible for tracing illegal money transfer. This Unit has agreements with different international anti-money laundering bodies. BFIU has agreements with the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), an inter-governmental

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body established in 1989 by the ministers of different countries, the Asia/Pacific Group on Money Laundering, an inter-governmental organisation for combating money laundering, terrorist financing and proliferation financing of weapons of mass destruction, and Egmont Group, a platform of 170 Financial Intelligence Units (FIUs) for securing exchange of expertise and financial intelligence to combat money-laundering and terrorist financing.

According to minutes of the meeting held on April this year, the foreign ministry has sent draft agreements to 10 countries for collecting necessary information, evidence, and legal support to recover laundered money.

These countries include Canada, the UK, the US, Singapore, Australia, Malaysia, the UAE, Switzerland, Thailand, and Hong Kong-China, where it is believed that the most money has been laundered by Bangladeshis.

Countries with Highest Risk factors in Money Laundering.

Note: Basel Anti Money Laundering Index (AML) indicates the Money Laundering Risk Factors.

In response, Australia requested additional information and sent a letter to Bangladesh, after receiving the draft agreement from Bangladesh.

Hong Kong authorities sent three draft agreements to Bangladesh, which are currently

being reviewed by the Public Security Division of the home ministry.

Interim Governments Chief Adviser Nobel laureate Dr. Muhammad Yunus formed Anti-Corruption Reform Commission on 11th September 2024 which will be led by Mr. Iftekharuzzaman who is the executive director of Transparency International Bangladesh. This commission will submit their report within three months. In addition, Bangladesh Bank has formed several task forces to assess the financial health of banks, find ways to resolve their crises, recover bad loans, and repatriate laundered money.

How Laundered Money has been Recovered Around the World?

Nigeria - Abacha Loot

Nigeria's former military ruler, Sani Abacha, looted an estimated \$5 billion during his regime (1993-1998) through corruption, money laundering, and embezzlement of public funds.

In 2004, Nigeria recovered \$500 million from Swiss banks after extensive legal proceedings and cooperation between Swiss authorities, the Nigerian government, and the World Bank.

In 2020, the U.S. and Jersey agreed to repatriate \$308 million of Abacha's funds that had been laundered through the U.S. financial system and held in

accounts in Jersey (a British Crown dependency).

Other recoveries were made in various countries, including the UK and Liechtenstein, bringing the total recovered to over \$1.3 billion.

The recovery process took many years due to legal hurdles, jurisdictional challenges, and international coordination, but it remains one of the largest asset recovery cases in history.

What we see is the special investigation panel (SIP) was formed to play a major role in recovering money that has been siphoned.

Malaysia - 1MDB Scandal

The 1Malaysia Development Berhad (1MDB) scandal involved massive embezzlement, where \$4.5 billion was laundered

through complex schemes involving international banks, politicians, and businessmen. Funds were allegedly siphoned from 1MDB, a state investment fund, to accounts held by individuals, including Malaysian officials.

In 2020, the U.S. Department of Justice (DOJ) reached a settlement with the American investment firm Goldman Sachs, which agreed to pay \$3.9 billion in fines, including \$2.5 billion directly to Malaysia, for its role in the scandal.

U.S. authorities also recovered over \$1 billion in assets tied to 1MDB, including luxury real estate, private jets, and expensive artwork. These assets were repatriated to Malaysia.

Several other recoveries were made in countries like Switzerland and Singapore, with assets frozen and returned.

Recovering 1MDB funds involved extensive international cooperation, tracing complex financial transactions, and prosecuting high-profile individuals, including former Malaysian Prime Minister Najib Razak.

There are many more case studies where laundered money has been recovered successfully like James Giffen Case (Kazakhstan), Fujimori/Montesinos Case (Peru), - Marcos Wealth (Philippines), Dos Santos Case (Angola) where swindled money has been recovered successfully.

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Conclusion

These cases show that while recovering laundered money is a long and challenging process, involving extensive legal battles, international cooperation, and asset tracing, it is achievable with the right mechanisms in place. Success depends on the legal frameworks for asset recovery, enforcement of anti-money laundering (AML) laws, and willingness of countries to cooperate. In Bangladesh perspective the matter is more challenging since our different controllable frameworks are extensively politicised which is why our hopes nipped in the bud. The fear persist who will bell the cat and fortunately martyrdom of hundreds has created an opportunity for new dawn. Are we really want to do this?

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Root Causes of a Tax Unresponsive Generation of Bangladesh

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The income tax laws of the Indian subcontinent have a long history of more than one hundred-year-old, starting from the Income Tax Act which was first introduced in 1860. Bangladesh showed strong resilience and dynamism by rising rapidly from the ruins of a war-devasted economy in 1972. In 2015, Bangladesh crossed the threshold of the World Bank-defined lower middle-income country category. Bangladesh now aspires to achieve upper middle-income country status and eliminate extreme poverty by FY2031. The target GDP growth rate from FY2019 to FY2031 is around 9% per year.

The tax to GDP ratio has grown modestly over the past 28 years. In the recent years (FY2010-FY2023), the tax to GDP ratio has basically stagnated, fluctuating around 9% of GDP. This is the lowest tax performance in South Asia and among the lowest in the world.

Fundamental Pillars of a Good Tax System

Many characteristics, which were thought to be the pillars of an effective tax system have been discussed by different scholars. The below five are generally considered as the minimum.

- **Fairness:** It means that fairness or equity is a fair share of the taxes that everyone should pay. The weight and burden of taxation should be balanced considering ability to pay tax.

- **Adequacy:** One of the most fundamental principles of a good tax system for a developing country is that it should provide the government with sufficient money to enable it to carry out its expanding welfare and development operations.
- **Simplicity:** Simplicity means a maze of fees, formats, and filing requirements can be avoided by taxpayers. A good tax system will improve taxpayers' understanding of the system and reduce compliance costs and effort.
- **Transparency:** This refers to the ease with which taxpayers and leaders can learn about the tax system and how tax money is spent.
- **Ease of Administration:** Either taxpayers or tax collectors do not find the system too cumbersome or expensive. The rules are generally known and pretty straightforward; forms are not too complex; and in proportion to the amount collected, the cost of collecting a tax should be very little.

A Quick Evaluation

In order to assess the merits of a tax system, it must be considered as its whole. For a tax system to be good, it can't only have all good taxes and no bad ones. The state is unable to raise sufficient revenue while

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pleasing taxpayers only. As a result, it is important to understand that a good tax system does not imply a flawless tax system with only good taxes based on the canons of taxation. A good taxation system is one that mostly carries good taxes and meets most tax canons. Keeping this in mind, if the above pillars are taken to consideration, a quick review of the present taxation system of Bangladesh might result into the below assertions.

Bangladesh's taxation system is regressive, allowing it to collect more money from the poor than from the rich. Rather than enhancing the tax net, the current taxation system is focused mostly on milking the same bunch of tax payers.

Through the taxation system, the government of Bangladesh

always lacks collection of adequate revenue to support its need for regular expenditures and implementation of development goals results into huge deficit budget in every fiscal year.

The taxation system of Bangladesh can be termed as most complex and tax payers' unfriendly system which encompasses of fierce processes, bureaucratic complexities and unclear guidance to tax payers.

Openness and accountability in the taxation system was actually never emphasized by any government of Bangladesh to make this impactful and appreciable by different peoples' forum of the country. The budget discussion held by NBR once in a year is the least effort that has so far been made by the previous governments.

Towards the Solution

This is a million-dollar question to address, even if all the above fundamental problems are solved, will the people of Bangladesh be intending to pay their due tax to the government?

At first let us have a look on a picture that encompasses the below data points.

- Bangladesh has one of the lowest tax-to-GDP ratios in the world, even though it posted high economic growth over the past decade. Tax collection Vs GDP (lowest) 7.8% in Dec 2023
- Nearly 59 percent of one crore TINs did not file tax returns in the just-concluded fiscal year of 2023-24
- The top 1 percent of taxpayers pay 26% tax
- Only around 2.5% of total population of the country pays tax

This is true that corruption, administrative weakness, complex tax rules, lack of awareness, the scope of money laundering, cash transaction in business, etc., are the significant causes of the low tax-to-GDP contribution in Bangladesh. In addition, the absence of a culture of tax payment and pro-tax mind set is responsible as poor incentive for people to become a tax payer.

People are Skeptical on Tax Payment

Tax evasion or tax avoidance is more or less a common practice in Bangladesh, the extent of which varies. The multinationals are compliant in tax payments whereas Local corporate houses do also pay tax on profits regularly, but it is not unusual on their part to play with numbers to pay less than actual payable taxes.

The National Board of Revenue (NBR), reportedly, has tried to bring tax-evading firms under the tax net in recent years, but with no notable success.

The employees working in the organized manufacturing and service sectors are among the people who pay taxes regularly. The management at the end of every month deducts the tax amount from their salaries and deposits the same in the public exchequer. Most others are found reluctant to pay taxes. This is why the contribution of direct tax is poor in the total tax collection and the share of tax paid by individuals is insignificant in total direct tax collection of Bangladesh.

What People Expect to Pay Tax

There are several factors that people expect to be willing to pay taxes:

1. Fairness of the tax system: When people believe the tax system is equitable, with everyone paying their fair share, they are more likely to be compliant. This includes transparency around how tax revenues are used.
2. Quality of public services: When people see that their tax moneys are funding essential public goods and services like infrastructure, education, healthcare, and public safety, they are generally more willing to contribute.
3. Trust in government: If citizens have faith that their elected officials are using tax revenue responsibly and effectively, they will be more inclined to fulfill their tax obligations.
4. Sense of civic duty: Many people are motivated by a belief that paying taxes is a

responsible and necessary part of being a member of society. Appeals to this civic mindset can encourage compliance.

5. Simplicity of the tax code: Complex, confusing tax laws make compliance more burdensome and can undermine voluntary payment. Streamlining the system can boost willingness.
6. Tangible benefits: If people can directly see the impact of their tax contributions, such as new infrastructure projects or social programs, they may feel more motivated to pay.

Ultimately, along with the above, a combination of fair and transparent policies, quality public services, and a sense of civic responsibility tend to foster a culture where people are induced to pay their fair share of taxes.

In order to achieve expansion of tax net to help generate more revenues for the government, it will be important to find out the reasons behind people's reluctance to pay taxes.

GDP per capita	Tax revenue (% of GDP)	Income taxes (% of total taxes)	Corporate income taxes (% of total income taxes)
All developing	17.6	31.2	42.3
Developed	25.0	54.3	17.8
Bangladesh (FY2024)	8.7	32	51.0

- Source: Gordon and Li ([Reference Gordon and Li2005](#)).

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Gap Between Tax Payers' Expectation and Reality in Bangladesh

- People would like to pay taxes in a simple and transparent manner. Taxation system with regard to determination and payment of tax in Bangladesh is still complex and troublesome.
- The citizens do not know the tax payment benefits, which are not clearly defined in Bangladesh. Social benefits, health benefits, education benefits, security of life and accidents-all are uncertain for a taxpayer. Corporate houses do not find level playing field and policy supports from the government.

- The payment of taxes to the government cannot assure a secure life for a taxpayer, even though taxpayers would surely be happy to pay taxes if the policies are simple and meaningful.
- The weakness on the demand side raises an important political economy issue. Bangladeshis are unwilling to pay taxes because they do not feel that resources are used effectively. This has been evidenced that the politicians and the system encourage pilferage of government funds sourced from taxes to a large extent when used in the implementation of public projects.

- There is at least some degree of truth that adequate tax collection is not possible in Bangladesh as citizens cannot see more and better public service provision in areas related to transport, water, sanitation, and drainage.
- This is a general perception which matches with reality that the public financial management system is full of corruption and inefficiency. This ends up with as in adequate use of taxes for the betterment of the people of the country.

Measures to Build a tax Enthusiast Nation

The size of an informal economy is one of the key reasons for tax losses by an economy.

Size of Informal Economy and the Associated Tax Loss in Bangladesh

Year	Size of the Economy (GDP) (in billion BDT)	Informal Economy as a % of official GDP	Size of Informal Economy (in billion BDT)	Tax Loss (in billion BDT)
2010	7975.4	35.54	2834.71	222.09
2011	9158.3	35.39	3241.28	281.54
2012	10552.0	35.20	3714.07	335.18
2013	11989.2	35.04	4201.52	376.56
2014	13436.7	34.93	4693.43	405.30
2015	15158.0	34.65	5251.63	446.30
2016	17328.6	34.77	6025.03	440.85
2017	19758.2	34.66	6847.84	479.15
2018	22504.8	34.65	7798.81	602.99
2021	35301.85	34.20	10661.16	842.23

Source: World Economics

(<https://www.worldeconomics.com>) and 'Bangladesh National Accounts Statistics' Data.

Though the size of the informal economy as proportion to the official GDP decreased over time, the tax loss in absolute terms due to the shadow economy increased. Over ten years (2010-2021), the volume of tax loss due to the shadow economy increased by four times from BDT 222 billion in 2010 to BDT 842 billion in 2021.

Aiming the greater revenue collection, actions should be taken to reform the entire taxation system of Bangladesh to ensure the proper implementation of basic required features of a modern and pragmatic taxation system. All the reform initiatives can be executed separately in short term and long-term streams. Earning credibility with regard to the taxation system that it works for the betterment of the citizens of the country will take time. Because it is important to change peoples' perception

through demonstration of the impact of the changes that would be made in tax policies, taxation system, tax administration and the public financial management.

In short term, reforms on the direct tax systems should aim at reduction of exemptions/deductions and tax holidays, taxation of capital gains, and harmonization of corporate and individual income tax rates to improve equity and efficiency of the direct tax system.

The generous tax rate for capital gains and de facto exemption of agricultural income creates horizontal inequities. Broadening the base of the income tax by eliminating special treatments would improve the horizontal equity of the tax, and make it fairer for all types of taxpayers.

Like most other countries, a fundamental reform of the tax system will be a challenging task both politically and administratively. Despite political commitments for fundamental reforms, there are vested groups in the business community and tax administration who would like to maintain the status quo and resist major changes. This will take at least three years, a longer time than bringing the changes in the current structure. In addition to extensive consultations with the stakeholders, massive publicity campaigns will need to be undertaken to create awareness among the taxpayers about the reforms. The tax payers should be informed as to why such reforms would be needed to safeguard their enhanced rights and obligations. Taxpayers' education campaigns will also be beneficial.

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Conclusion

In the recent past regimes, the trust of the people of the country on the truthfulness, trustworthiness and efficiency of the revenue collection and utilization of the same has dropped to virtually zero. This is one of the driving factors of increasing the size of informal economy of Bangladesh. In addition to all the above changes, it has become crucial to establish trust on the entire financial system of the government through making a

true and correct financial information system of the government accessible for the general people of the country as well as ensuring efficient spending of the collected revenue of the government for the wellbeing of the people of the country. The transitoriness of the income and the expenditure of the government which did never exist if founded, can certainly play a major role in enhancing the tax net thereby increasing tax revenues in Bangladesh.

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An Analysis of Factors Affecting the GDP Growth: Evidence from Bangladesh

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Abstract

This study investigates the effects of the unemployment rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate on the GDP growth of Bangladesh. This research utilized a quantitative approach to analyze the impact of the unemployment rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate using multiple linear regression. The correlation analysis reveals significant positive relationships between GDP growth and both the exchange rate and unemployment rate. The regression coefficients indicate that the exchange rate significantly enhances GDP growth, while the unemployment rate has a marginally significant negative impact, and the inflation rate's effect is minimal. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers to optimize economic growth and strategy.

Keywords

Unemployment rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, GDP, Bangladesh.

Introduction

In today's globalized economy, understanding the intricate interplay between various macroeconomic indicators is crucial for policymakers, economists, and investors alike. Among these indicators, inflation, exchange rates, and unemployment rates stand out as key determinants shaping the trajectory of economic growth (Lal et al., 2023; Ulug et al., 2023). The dynamics between

these factors are complex, with each exerting its unique influence on the overall economic landscape.

While these macroeconomic indicators impact all nations, the nature and extent of their effects can vary significantly depending on a country's level of economic development, institutional framework, and policy response mechanisms (Fatas and Mihov, 2013). Understanding these variations is crucial for devising tailored strategies to promote sustainable growth and resilience in diverse economic contexts. In developing economies, the relationship between inflation, exchange rates, unemployment rates, and economic growth is often characterized by heightened volatility and structural vulnerabilities (Gnangnon, 2016, 2021). High levels of inflation, driven by factors such as supply constraints, fiscal imbalances, and external shocks, can erode purchasing power, undermine investor confidence, and impede long-term investment (Ali and Asfaw, 2023; Ha et al., 2019; Kaltenbrunner and Paineira, 2017). In such contexts, policymakers often face the dual challenge of combating inflationary pressures while fostering inclusive growth and employment opportunities (Ali, 2023; Chaikin and Usiuk, 2019; Twinoburyo and Odhiambo, 2018). Conversely, low inflation (less than 2%) or deflation may signal weak demand and economic stagnation (Benigno

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and Fornaro, 2018; Grinin and Korotayev, 2018).

Exchange rate fluctuations can exacerbate these challenges, particularly in economies heavily reliant on exports/imports or vulnerable to external shocks (Briguglio, 2016; Sikarwar, 2018). While depreciation may enhance export competitiveness and stimulate growth in the short term, it can also fuel inflationary pressures and exacerbate balance of payments imbalances (Ali, 2023; Kolte et al., 2021). Conversely, appreciation may dampen export prospects and constrain growth, especially in export-oriented sectors such as manufacturing and agriculture (Aragie et al., 2013; Yildirim and Ivrendi 2016).

Unemployment rates, particularly among youth and marginalized groups, pose significant obstacles to economic development in many developing economies (Banks, 2016; Bartolucci et al., 2018). Structural rigidities, inadequate

skill mismatches, and limited access to finance often perpetuate high levels of unemployment and underemployment, constraining productivity and stifling growth potential (Agenor and Lim, 2018). High unemployment rates not only lead to lost output and income but also impose social costs in the form of increased poverty and inequality (Efrianti et al., 2018; Kayode et al., 2014). Conversely, low unemployment rates can strain labor markets, potentially fueling wage inflation and posing challenges for businesses (Lu et al., 2022).

Understanding the relationships between inflation, exchange rates, unemployment rates, and GDP growth is essential for formulating effective macroeconomic policies and fostering sustainable development. Bangladesh stands as a significant developing market economy within South Asia, holding the position as the region's second-largest economy. Globally, it ranks 35th in nominal terms and 25th by purchasing

power parity, with many financial institutions identifying it as one of the Next Eleven nations. Over recent decades, Bangladesh has transitioned from a frontier market to an emerging one, with GDP growth consistently exceeding 6 percent.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic hit hard, leading to a sharp decline with a record low of 3.42% growth in 2019-20. This downturn was exacerbated by macroeconomic mismanagement, resulting in uncontrolled inflation and diminished purchasing power among the population. Moreover, the crisis in foreign currency reserves compelled restrictions on imports, with inadequacies in foreign exchange market management exacerbating the situation. Consequently, high inflation, unemployment, and foreign currency mismanagement have significantly hampered the country's economic stability. Hence, this study aims to analyze the impact of inflation, unemployment, and exchange rates on Bangladesh's GDP growth, outlining the following research objectives.

The objectives of this paper are to examine the following issues:

1. To examine the effect of inflation rate on the GDP growth rate in the Bangladesh economy
2. To analyze the impact of exchange rate on the GDP growth rate in the Bangladesh economy

3. To investigate the impact of unemployment rate on the GDP growth rate in the Bangladesh economy

To achieve the stated objective, the paper will review the literature before justifying the chosen research method. Prior to drawing conclusions, the findings will be reported and discussed in detail.

Literature Review

This article aims to review and synthesize existing literature on the effects of macroeconomic indicators like unemployment, inflation, and exchange rate on GDP growth.

Unemployment and GDP Growth

The relationship between unemployment and GDP growth is complex and multifaceted, influenced by various economic, social, and institutional factors. Understanding the dynamics

between these two variables is crucial for formulating effective economic policies aimed at achieving stable and sustainable growth. According to Okun's law, there is a negative relationship between unemployment and GDP growth. Okun's law implies that for every 1% increase in unemployment above the natural rate, GDP will decrease by 2% (Chuttoo, 2020). However, the validity of Okun's law has been debated, particularly in the context of structural changes in the labor market and variations in the natural rate of unemployment over time (Lim et al., 2021; Ududu & Nnachi, 2017).

Empirical studies investigating the relationship between unemployment and GDP growth have produced mixed findings, reflecting the complexity of the relationship and the influence of various factors (Ozcebe & Ozkan, 2017; Shabbir et al., 2021). Some studies have found

evidence supporting the existence of a negative relationship between unemployment and GDP growth, consistent with Okun's law. For example, research by Marques et al. (2017) found a significant negative correlation between changes in unemployment and GDP growth across a sample of OECD countries.

However, other studies have questioned the robustness of this relationship, highlighting the importance of factors such as labor market flexibility, structural reforms, and technological advancements (Liotti, 2020). For instance, research by Adarkwa et al. (2017) argued that the negative relationship between unemployment and GDP growth may have weakened over time due to increased labor market flexibility and the rise of the service sector. High levels of unemployment not only represent a waste of productive resources but also have adverse social and psychological consequences (Mousteri et al., 2018).

The relationship between unemployment and GDP growth has significant implications for economic policy formulation. Unemployment rates, particularly long-term unemployment, have been shown to have adverse effects on economic growth, productivity, and social cohesion (Mousteri et al., 2018; Shabbir et al., 2021). Policies aimed at reducing structural unemployment through

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education and training programs, labor market reforms, and targeted fiscal stimulus can enhance the economy's growth potential and inclusivity (Mian et al., 2022). However, the effectiveness of such policies hinges on their design, implementation, and coordination with other macroeconomic measures (Blanchard et al., 2018).

Inflation and GDP Growth

Various economic schools offer differing perspectives on the relationship between inflation and GDP growth. According to Keynesian economics, there exists a positive correlation between inflation and GDP growth. They argue that previous saving is not a prerequisite for GDP expansion (Girdzijauskas et al., 2022). Dornbusch (1996) posits that in the short term, the aggregate demand curve slopes upwards

rather than being vertical, implying that changes in demand impact both prices and output. In conditions of full employment, increasing the money supply boosts aggregate demand and output, while in situations of underemployment, it leads to inflation and lower real interest rates, thereby encouraging capital intensity and stimulating output and saving (Ali, 2023; Girdzijauskas et al., 2022). Moreover, this theory suggests that a low real interest rate fosters growth.

The Classical school contributes to growth theory by emphasizing self-reinforcement. Li (2004) contend that investment stems from savings, implying that income distribution determines a nation's GDP growth rate. While relative prices, employment, and output may influence nominal inflation, they do not alter the GDP growth trajectory in a

steady state (Chen, 2020). The Classical school maintains a neutral stance regarding this relationship. In contrast to the Classical and Keynesian schools, the Neo-classical school presents divergent perspectives among scholars. For instance, Stockman (1981) argues that rising inflation leads to a reduction in output and people's welfare. As inflation erodes the purchasing power of money, individuals decrease their purchases of both consumer goods and capital, ultimately diminishing the steady-state level of output.

Despite ongoing theoretical debates, empirical studies shed light on the relationship between inflation and GDP growth. Ghosh and Phillips (1998) conducted a study using a sample of 145 countries to examine the impact of GDP per capita on Consumer Price Inflation and found a nonlinear relationship. They discovered that high inflation rates, particularly above 2.5 percent, have a negative effect on GDP growth, indicating that hyperinflation leads to a decline in economic growth. Conversely, at lower inflation rates, typically between 2 to 3 percent, the relationship between inflation and GDP growth tends to be positive.

Sarel (1996) took a different approach, employing a structural break model to analyze the relationship. His findings confirmed the adverse effect of inflation on GDP growth, particularly at inflation

levels exceeding 8 percent, where the effect was strongly negative, significant, and robust. At inflation rates below 8 percent, the impact on GDP growth was either negligible or slightly positive. Sattarov (2011) observed that a 10 percent increase in inflation corresponded to a decrease in the GDP growth rate by 0.2 to 0.3 percent points per year in his study. Similarly, Hossin (2015) argued for a negative relationship between double digit inflation and GDP growth.

Exchange Rate and GDP Growth

In economic studies, the exchange rate is recognized as a crucial factor influencing both short- and long-term macroeconomic goals such as growth and development (Guzman et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2019). Ozata (2020) highlight the significance of exchange rate volatility, referring to the persistent fluctuations in

exchange rates, as it impacts economic activities significantly. Fraj et al. (2018) and Guzman et al. (2018) examined the impact of real exchange rate instability, concluding that maintaining a low level of exchange rate volatility is essential for fostering growth.

Other research has contended that the impact of exchange rate policy on the economic growth of nations varies, largely due to differences in exchange rate volatility between flexible and fixed exchange rate systems (Barguelli et al., 2018; Erdal and Pinar, 2019; Lartey, 2017). For example, Barguelli et al. (2018) discovered in their analysis of 45 developing and emerging countries that exchange rate volatility had a detrimental effect on economic growth under a flexible exchange rate regime. Additionally, studies focusing on Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries

have yielded mixed findings regarding the relationship between exchange rate fluctuations and macroeconomic performance. Olamide et al. (2022) observed an inverse correlation between exchange rate changes and GDP in some OECD nations.

The relationship between exchange rates and economic growth has also been extensively studied, with findings depending on factors such as country-specific characteristics, exchange rate regimes, and the presence of external shocks (Erdal and Pinar, 2019; Lartey, 2017). Flexible exchange rate regimes are often associated with greater macroeconomic stability and resilience to external shocks, allowing for efficient adjustment mechanisms (Guzman et al., 2018). However, fixed exchange rate regimes may promote export-led growth and price stability in the short term. Furthermore, managed floating exchange rate regimes have become increasingly prevalent in the global economy, with many countries opting for flexible exchange rate systems that allow for some degree of government intervention. However, the actual impact of managed floating exchange rates on GDP growth may vary depending on factors such as exchange rate volatility, trade openness, and capital mobility (Ehikioya, 2019).

The effects of unemployment, inflation, and exchange rates on economic growth vary across developing and developed

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economies, reflecting distinct structural characteristics, policy priorities, and institutional capacities. By understanding these differences and tailoring policy responses accordingly, policymakers can navigate the complexities of macroeconomic management and foster sustainable development in diverse economic contexts.

Methodology

Given the nature of research question, quantitative method is adopted. Creswell and Creswell (2017) argued that the quantitative method is ideal for hypothesis testing to verify positive, negative, or causal relationships. Through the use of hypotheses, this study answered research questions using multiple linear regression to draw certain remarks.

The study utilized existing data on Bangladesh's GDP growth,

inflation rate, exchange rate, and unemployment rate spanning from 1991 to 2022, gathered from various reputable sources such as the World Bank archives, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, and Bangladesh Bank reports. Using SPSS version 26, the researcher constructed a multiple linear regression model to examine how inflation, exchange rate, and unemployment rate collectively impact Bangladesh's GDP growth. The multiple regression model assessing the influence of inflation, exchange rate, and unemployment rate on GDP growth is expressed as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

Where:

- Y= GDP growth rate
- X₁= Unemployment rate
- X₂= Inflation rate
- X₃= Exchange rate

In this model, β_0 is the intercept term. β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 are the regression coefficients. The coefficients (β_1 , β_2 , and β_3) indicate the magnitude and direction of the relationship between each independent variable and GDP growth. ϵ is the error term representing unexplained variability. Based on the multiple regression model, the following hypotheses are formulated as follows:

- H₀1: There is no significant relationship between unemployment rate and GDP growth in Bangladesh.
- H₀2: There is no significant relationship between inflation rate and GDP growth in Bangladesh.
- H₀3: There is no significant relationship between exchange rate and GDP growth in Bangladesh.

Results and Discussions

The analysis of the economic variables, including GDP growth, unemployment rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate, reveals insightful trends and distributions crucial for understanding the economic landscape. The following table provides a comprehensive statistical overview of the four economic variables, showing their range (minimum and maximum), central tendency (mean), dispersion (standard deviation), and the shape of their distributions (skewness and kurtosis) along with the associated standard errors for skewness and kurtosis.

Table 1: Statistical overview of the variables

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
GDP growth	3.448	7.882	5.644	1.189	-0.126	0.414	-0.871	0.809
Unemployment rate	2.200	5.209	3.770	0.902	-0.415	0.414	-1.045	0.809
Inflation rate	2.007	11.395	6.144	2.224	0.117	0.414	0.179	0.809
Exchange rate	35.680	86.300	63.058	16.780	-0.232	0.414	-1.408	0.809

Table 2: Correlation analysis among variables

Variables		GDP Growth	Unemployment rate	Inflation rate	Exchange rate
GDP Growth	Pearson Correlation	1	.495**	.320	.683**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004	.074	.000
Unemployment rate	Pearson Correlation	.495**	1	.188	.898**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004		.303	.000
Inflation rate	Pearson Correlation	.320	.188	1	.271
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.074	.303		.134
Exchange rate	Pearson Correlation	.683**	.898**	.271	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.134	

The GDP growth rate, ranging from 3.448 to 7.882 with an average of 5.644, shows moderate variability. Similarly, the unemployment rate, with values between 2.200 and 5.209 and an average of 3.770, also exhibits moderate variability. The inflation rate, which spans from 2.007 to 11.395 with a mean of 6.144, shows significant variability. However, the exchange rate, fluctuating widely between 35.680 and 86.300 and averaging 63.058, demonstrates substantial variability. In addition, according to Byrne (2013), data is deemed normal if the skewness falls between 32, and the kurtosis falls between 37. In this case, the skewness and kurtosis values fall inside Bryne's (2013) range.

The correlation analysis reveals significant relationships among key economic variables, providing critical insights into their interdependencies. GDP growth shows a strong positive correlation with the exchange rate ($r = .683$, $p < .01$), suggesting that as GDP growth increases, the exchange rate also tends to increase significantly. Additionally, GDP growth is moderately positively correlated with the unemployment rate ($r = .495$, $p < .01$), indicating that higher GDP growth is associated with a lower unemployment rate. However, the correlation between GDP growth and inflation rate ($r = .320$, $p = .074$) is not statistically significant at the 0.01 level. The

unemployment rate is strongly positively correlated with the exchange rate ($r = .898$, $p < .01$), indicating that higher unemployment rates are associated with higher exchange rates. The relationship between the unemployment rate and the inflation rate ($r = .188$, $p = .303$) is not significant. Lastly, the inflation rate has a weak and non-significant positive correlation with the exchange rate ($r = .271$, $p = .134$). These findings underscore the intricate dynamics between economic growth, employment, and currency valuation, which are crucial for informed economic policy and decision-making.

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Table 3: Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.742a	0.551	0.503	0.838

a Predictors: (Constant), Exchange rate, Inflation rate, Unemployment Rate

Table 4: ANOVA result

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.127	3	8.042	11.446	.000 ^b
	Residual	19.674	28	0.703		
	Total	43.801	31			

a Dependent Variable: GDP Growth
b Predictors: (Constant), Exchange rate, Inflation rate, Unemployment Rate

Table 5: Multiple Regression analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.918	0.717		4.068	0.000
	Unemployment Rate	-0.768	0.383	-0.583	-2.004	0.055
	Inflation rate	0.059	0.071	0.110	0.832	0.412
	Exchange rate	0.083	0.021	1.177	3.965	0.000

a Dependent Variable: GDP Growth

The multiple correlation coefficient (R) is .742, suggesting a strong positive relationship between the dependent variable and the combined predictors. The R Square value of 0.551 indicates that approximately 55.1% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the model, while the Adjusted R Square value of 0.503 accounts for the number of predictors in the model, providing a more accurate measure of the goodness-of-fit. The standard error of the estimate is 0.838, which measures the average

distance that the observed values fall from the regression line.

The ANOVA table provides an analysis of variance for the regression model predicting GDP growth based on exchange rate, inflation rate, and unemployment rate. The regression model is statistically significant, as indicated by the F-value of 11.446 and a p-value of .000, which is well below the conventional threshold of 0.01. This suggests that the predictors collectively have a significant impact on GDP

growth. The sum of squares for the regression is 24.127, with 3 degrees of freedom, resulting in a mean square of 8.042. The residual sum of squares is 19.674 with 28 degrees of freedom, leading to a mean square of 0.703. The total sum of squares is 43.801, representing the total variance in GDP growth. These results confirm that the model significantly explains the variation in GDP growth, demonstrating the importance of the exchange rate, inflation rate, and unemployment rate as predictors.

Based on the calculations, the following multiple linear regression model has been developed.

$$Y = 2.918 - 0.768X_1 + 0.059 X_2 + 0.083X_3 + \epsilon$$

The coefficients table provides detailed information about the contributions of the predictors—unemployment rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate—to the regression model predicting GDP growth. The constant term (intercept) is 2.918, with a standard error of 0.717, and is statistically significant ($t = 4.068$, $p < .001$), indicating that the average GDP growth rate is 2.918 when all predictors are zero. Among the predictors, the unemployment rate (X_1) shows a negative association with GDP growth

(coefficient = -0.768 , $p = 0.055$), suggesting that higher unemployment may slightly reduce growth, though this relationship is marginally significant. Hence, the research hypothesis H_{01} is rejected.

Marques et al. (2017) explained this trend by finding a negative correlation between changes in unemployment and GDP growth across a sample of OECD countries. However, other studies have questioned the strength of this relationship, emphasising the importance of factors such as labour market flexibility, structural reforms, and technological advancements (Liotti, 2020). Adarkwa et al. (2017) found that the negative correlation between unemployment and GDP growth has weakened over

time due to increased labour market flexibility and the rise of the service sector.

Conversely, the inflation rate (X_2) has a minimal and non-significant effect on GDP growth (coefficient = 0.059 , $p = 0.412$). Thus, the research hypothesis H_{02} is supported. These findings are consistent with the analyses conducted by Oduor et al. (2021) and Opeyemi (2020), which also observed that inflation does not have a significant impact on GDP growth. Both studies emphasized that the relationship between inflation and GDP growth is influenced by a variety of other economic variables, suggesting that the effect of inflation on economic growth is not straightforward and can be moderated or mediated by other factors in the economy.

Additionally, the exchange rate (X_3) has a highly significant positive impact on GDP growth, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.083 ($p < .001$), highlighting its crucial role in economic expansion. Therefore, the research hypothesis H_{03} is supported. These findings align with the research of other scholars, suggesting that the exchange rate policy has a significant impact on economic growth, varying with different policies. Specifically, Barguelli et al. (2018) and Erdal and Pinar (2019) found that different exchange rate policies (fixed, flexible, and managed floating) could have varying effects on economic growth. Moreover, the

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impact of managed floating exchange rates on GDP growth may be influenced by factors such as exchange rate volatility, trade openness, and capital mobility, as highlighted by Ehikioya (2019). These factors can create varying outcomes for a country's economic growth, making it critical to consider them when adopting an exchange rate policy.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The statistical analysis of economic data provides a detailed understanding of the factors influencing GDP growth. Descriptive statistics reveal moderate variability in GDP growth and unemployment rate, with higher variability in inflation and exchange rates. The correlation analysis identifies significant positive relationships between GDP growth and both the exchange rate and

unemployment rate, while the inflation rate shows no significant correlations. Regression analysis explains 55.1% of the variance in GDP growth, with the exchange rate emerging as the most significant positive predictor. The coefficients further illustrate that while the exchange rate significantly boosts GDP growth, the unemployment rate has a marginally significant negative effect, and the inflation rate's impact is negligible. These findings highlight the critical roles of exchange rate management and unemployment reduction in promoting economic growth.

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that policymakers prioritize a stable and favorable exchange rate policy, recognizing its significant positive impact on GDP growth. Specifically, adopting a suitable exchange

rate system that provides stability and flexibility could help optimize economic growth. Additionally, policies aimed at reducing unemployment should be a key focus, considering the marginally significant negative relationship between higher unemployment and GDP growth. This could be achieved through structural reforms that improve labor market flexibility and increase employment opportunities in the service sector. Further, maintaining a stable inflation rate should be a priority, even though its direct impact on GDP growth may be minor, as it is essential for overall economic stability. Lastly, these recommendations underscore the need for a comprehensive approach that considers the interdependent nature of these variables and their effects on the economy, thereby ensuring that policies are designed to provide a conducive environment for growth.

Limitations and Further Research

The research primarily focuses on examining the effects of inflation, exchange rate, and unemployment rate on GDP growth. While it is acknowledged that there are numerous other factors contributing to economic growth, such as investment levels, technological advancements, trade balance, government policies, and human capital development, these factors were not included in the scope of this study for several reasons.

The researcher opted for a more focused approach to ensure a thorough and detailed analysis of the chosen variables. By limiting the scope to these three factors, the study was able to employ a more in-depth analysis and draw clearer conclusions about their individual effects on GDP growth. Additionally, the availability and reliability of secondary data for these specific variables were key considerations in determining the scope of the research. Given the multifaceted nature of economic growth, future research could explore the additional factors mentioned to gain deeper insights into their influence on GDP.

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Retirement Redefined: Strategic Planning for a Secure Future in Bangladesh

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Introduction

Retirement in Bangladesh was viewed as a golden period of life, akin to an endless leisure at a serene home with family. People eagerly anticipated the day they could step away from their daily grind, imagining a future filled with relaxation, hobbies, and quality time with family and friends. The assurance of approved pension and employee benefit schemes made this dream seem easily attainable.

However, this idyllic vision of retirement has dramatically shifted. In today's fast-paced world, with rising costs of living, healthcare, longer lifespans, and the erosion of traditional support systems, the notion of a carefree retirement has become more challenging to achieve. The increasing financial demands and the transition from joint family structures to nuclear families mean that many retirees find themselves facing financial insecurity and uncertainty.

In Bangladesh, these changes are acutely felt. The retirement landscape has become more complex, necessitating careful planning and proactive financial management. Unlike the past, where pensions and family support were sufficient, today's retirees need to be more self-reliant and financially savvy. The shift from guaranteed pension schemes to contribution-based plans like provident funds and private

pensions places the onus on individuals to save and invest wisely for their future.

Moreover, the informal sector, which employs a significant portion of the Bangladeshi workforce, often lacks formal retirement benefits, leaving many without a financial safety net. This reality underscores the importance of early and diversified retirement planning to ensure a comfortable and secure retirement.

This article aims to shed light on the evolving retirement scenario in Bangladesh, drawing lessons from real-life stories of retirees who faced unexpected challenges. It provides practical strategies and insights to help future retirees navigate this new landscape, ensuring they can achieve the financial security and peace of mind they deserve. By taking proactive steps today, individuals can transform their retirement from a period of uncertainty into a time of fulfillment and joy, much like the dream retirement once envisioned.

Retirement Plans in Bangladesh

Retirement plans in Bangladesh are evolving as the country progresses economically and socially. Historically, formal retirement planning has not been a widespread practice, with many people relying on government pension, Shanchaya Patra and personal savings for support in their old age. However, with increasing

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life expectancy and changes in family structures, the need for structured retirement plans is growing.

Government and Public Sector Pensions

- 1. Government Pension Scheme:** The primary retirement plan available is the government pension scheme for public sector employees. This plan provides a monthly pension based on the employee's final salary and length of service. The scheme ensures a steady income for retired government workers and includes provisions for family pensions for dependents after the retiree's death.
- 2. Gratuity and Provident Fund:** Public sector employees also benefit from gratuity payments and provident funds. The

provident fund is a compulsory, contributory savings scheme where both the employer and the employee contribute a portion of the salary. Upon retirement, the accumulated fund is paid out as a lump sum.

Private Sector Retirement Plans

- 1. Recognized Provident Fund:** Private companies offer contributory provident funds, where employees can contribute a part of their salary, which is matched by the employer. This fund accumulates over the employee's career and is disbursed at retirement.
- 2. Gratuity Fund:** The concept of private gratuity funds in Bangladesh is gaining traction. Financial institutions, insurance companies and many large

1. companies are beginning to offer such schemes where eligible employees; after a certain period of employment (for example 5 years), and on separation from the service are paid a month's basic salary for every completed year of service.

Challenges and Future Directions

- 1. Coverage and Awareness:** One of the significant challenges is the low coverage of formal retirement plans. A large portion of the workforce, particularly in the informal sector, does not have access to structured retirement benefits. Increasing awareness and expanding coverage to include informal sector workers are critical areas for development.
- 2. Financial Literacy:** Improving financial literacy is essential to help individuals understand the importance of retirement planning and the options available to them. This can encourage more people to start saving early and invest in retirement plans.
- 3. Policy Reforms:** The government is working on policy reforms to enhance the retirement system. This includes improving the regulatory framework for private pension plans and exploring options to extend

social security benefits to a broader segment of the population.

In summary, while traditional familial support has been the norm for retirees in Bangladesh, there is a growing shift towards structured retirement plans. The government's pension schemes, along with emerging private sector options, are steps towards ensuring financial security for the aging population. However, increasing coverage and financial literacy

remain key challenges to be addressed for a more inclusive retirement system in Bangladesh.

Real-Life Stories of Retirement Challenges in Bangladesh

Story 1: The Struggle of Delwar Hossain

Delwar Hossain, a retired school teacher from a rural area in Bangladesh, faced significant hardships after retirement.

Having dedicated over 30 years to teaching, Delwar retired with a modest government pension. However, the rising cost of living and healthcare expenses quickly outpaced his pension income.

Delwar's health deteriorated soon after retirement, and his medical bills became a heavy financial burden. With no substantial savings or additional income, he had to rely on his children for financial support. The lack of a robust retirement savings plan left him vulnerable,

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highlighting the importance of financial planning and the limitations of relying solely on government pensions.

Story 2: Shakila Banu's Uncertain Future

Shakila Banu, a former garment factory worker, represents another common scenario. The informal nature of her employment meant she had no access to formal retirement benefits like pensions or provident funds. After decades of hard work, Banu retired with no savings.

Her situation was further compounded by limited social security support. She now depends on her extended family for survival. Banu's story underscores the challenges faced by informal sector workers in Bangladesh, who often retire without any financial safety net.

Story 3: Shamsul Haque's Healthcare Dilemma

Shamsul Haque, a retired government clerk, enjoyed a stable job with a modest pension. However, his retirement years were plagued by health issues, particularly chronic illnesses that required expensive treatments. Although he received a government pension, it was insufficient to cover his high medical expenses.

Shamsul had to sell his ancestral land to pay for his healthcare, leaving him with no assets. His story illustrates the critical need for comprehensive retirement planning, including adequate healthcare provisions, which are often overlooked.

Story 4: The Plight of Anwara Khatun

Anwara Khatun, a retired nurse, faced a different set of

challenges. Despite her long service in the healthcare sector, her pension was meager due to the low salary scale in her profession. Her children lived abroad and could not provide regular financial support.

Anwara struggled to maintain her standard of living and often had to compromise on essential needs. Her situation highlights the disparity in retirement benefits across different professions and the inadequacy of pensions for certain public sector employees.

Key Takeaways

These real-life stories from Bangladesh shed light on several critical issues:

- 1. Insufficient Pensions:** Many retirees, especially from the public sector, find that their pensions do not keep pace with inflation and rising living costs.
- 2. Lack of Savings:** A significant portion of the population, particularly those in informal sectors, retire without any savings or retirement plans.
- 3. Healthcare Costs:** High medical expenses are a major challenge for retirees, often leading to financial distress.
- 4. Dependence on Family:** Many retirees rely heavily on their children or extended family for financial support, which can be uncertain and inadequate.

These narratives emphasize the need for comprehensive retirement planning, better social security measures, and increased financial literacy to ensure a more secure and dignified retirement for all.

Real-Life Stories of Happy Retirees in Bangladesh

Story 1: Najma Begum's Fulfilling Retirement

Najma Begum, a former school principal in Dhaka, retired after a long and fulfilling career in education. Having planned meticulously for her retirement, she invested in a combination of government bonds,

Shanchayapatra, fixed deposits in her early employment years and a private pension plan. Her disciplined approach to savings and investments ensured a steady flow of income post-retirement.

Najma is now able to enjoy her passion for gardening and spends quality time with her grandchildren. She also volunteers at a local non-profit organization that provides educational support to underprivileged children. Najma's story highlights the importance of early planning and disciplined saving, which have enabled her to lead a content and active retired life.

Story 2: Arif Ahmed's Entrepreneurial Journey

Arif Ahmed, a retired banker, always dreamed of starting his own business. Upon retirement, with a well-planned pension and substantial savings, he opened a small local café in Chittagong. His banking background helped him manage the business efficiently, and his café quickly became popular in the community.

Ahmed's entrepreneurial venture not only provides him with an additional income stream but also keeps him engaged and socially active. His story exemplifies how

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retirement can be a second opportunity to pursue passions and hobbies, making the golden years truly rewarding.

Story 3: Shahana Ahmed's Leisurely Life

Shahana Ahmed worked as a senior nurse at a renowned hospital in Sylhet. Throughout her career, she consistently contributed to her provident fund and invested in a private retirement savings plan. Upon retiring, she received a lump sum that allowed her to indulge in her love for reading and agriculture activities.

Shahana now owns various fruit gardens in Sylhet which provides her passive income stream all year round. She writes occasionally about her nursing experiences in local newspapers. Her proactive financial planning and passion for continuous learning have made her retirement a period of personal growth and fulfillment.

Story 4: Rezaul Karim's Peaceful Retirement

Rezaul Karim, a former government employee, retired to his ancestral village near Rajshahi. He had a secure government pension and savings from his provident fund. Rezaul used part of his savings to renovate his family home and cultivate a small piece of land.

Karim now enjoys a peaceful rural life, growing organic vegetables and fruits, which he sells at the local market. His involvement in farming keeps him physically active, and the sense of community in the village provides him with a supportive social network. Rezaul's story illustrates how returning to one's roots and engaging in meaningful activities can lead to a happy and content retirement.

These real-life stories from Bangladesh demonstrate that with proper planning, financial

discipline, and a positive outlook, retirement can indeed be a fulfilling and happy phase of life. Whether through hobbies, new ventures, or simply enjoying leisure time, these retirees have found ways to make their post-working years rewarding and joyful. Their experiences highlight the importance of early and strategic planning to ensure a secure and enjoyable retirement.

Conclusion

Planning for retirement is an essential step for ensuring financial security and maintaining a dignified standard of living in one's later years. In Bangladesh, where the retirement system is still developing, it is especially crucial to take proactive measures. The stories of the mentioned individuals underscore the challenges that many retirees face due to inadequate pensions, lack of savings, high healthcare costs, and heavy dependence on familial support.

To avoid these pitfalls and to ensure a more stable and comfortable retirement, consider the following comprehensive strategies:

- 1. Start Early:** An early start in saving for retirement allows your savings to grow through compound interest, significantly increasing your retirement fund over time. Even modest, regular

contributions can accumulate into a substantial fund.

2. Diversify Retirement Savings: Relying solely on government pensions may not be sufficient. Explore other retirement savings options such as provident funds, private pension plans, and investments in insurance plans. Diversification helps mitigate risks and can provide multiple streams of income during retirement. It is also important to make investments that can outpace inflation, such as stocks or real estate, to maintain your standard of living.

3. Budget for Healthcare: Healthcare costs can be a major financial burden in retirement. Plan ahead by budgeting for medical expenses and consider investing in health insurance to cover unforeseen medical bills. This can protect your retirement savings from being depleted by healthcare costs.

4. Improve Financial Literacy: Educate yourself about financial planning and retirement savings. Understanding different investment options, tax advantages, and the impact of inflation on your savings is crucial. Attend financial planning workshops, read

relevant books, or seek advice from financial planners to enhance your knowledge.

5. Maximize Employer Benefits: Take full advantage of any retirement benefits offered by your employer. This includes contributing to provident funds or any other retirement savings plans that provide employer matching contributions. These benefits can considerably boost the retirement savings.

6. Emergency Fund: Maintain an emergency fund to cover unexpected expenses without dipping into your

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retirement savings. This fund needs to be readily available and large enough to sustain living expenditures for a minimum of six months.

7. Regularly Review and Adjust Your Plan:

Retirement planning is not a one-time activity. Regularly review your retirement plan and adjust it according to changes in your income, expenses, and financial goals. Staying flexible and proactive helps ensure that your retirement plan remains on track.

Moreover, people in Bangladesh can also follow approaches provided by global experts to estimate how much one needs to save in order to retire comfortably. One such approach recommended by the Wall Street Journal's experts is the 80% preretirement Income Approach.

It states that most retirees can live on less than they earned during their working years. Replacing 80% of one's income means his/her lifestyle can essentially stay the same that is

because once you retire, you're no longer paying contributions to Provident Funds, High Income Taxes, weekly transportation costs to an office. So around one can live with 80% of the income he/she is currently earning. Provided that you pay off your long term loans and debts before retiring, and assuming a conservative inflation rate over the years.

By following these comprehensive strategies, future retirees in Bangladesh can build a robust financial foundation for their retirement. Early planning, diversification, and continuous financial education are key to achieving a secure and comfortable retirement. Learning from the experiences of others and taking proactive steps today can help you avoid common pitfalls and ensure a stable future.

Investing in your retirement is investing in your peace of mind. The more prepared you are, the more you can enjoy your retirement years without financial stress. Remember, the journey to a safe and secured retirement begins today.

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AI in Quality Management

How AI is revolutionizing the Quality Process

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Quality Mindset

Quality is getting it right. Right the first time and most of the time, size of the operation notwithstanding. Quality mindset, impeccable policies, procedures and work instructions underlie good quality management. Whether it is a Jamdani Saree (product) or drug manufacturing process quality is meeting the prescribed standards.

Quality is Meeting Customer Expectation

Quality is meeting or exceeding customer satisfaction consistently. That is a tall order. It calls for a lot of disciplined work which requires effective collaboration, proper documentation, data acquisition/ analysis, inspection and monitoring.

Manual Procedures Inadequate

Bigger the operation more challenging becomes the task of maintenance of the quality process and the overall quality management. Clearly manual systems with manual procedures, sample-based inspection is limiting. Post production defect detection in a manual system by fatigue prone and easily bored humans cannot ensure consistent quality. Point to note is that ISO (International Standards Organisation) established in 1943 released ISO 9001, standard for Quality Management System (QMS),

first in 1987 with last revision in 2015 or so are benchmarks used for QMS.

Technology Driving Quality Management

60s to 70s: Mainframe Based

Owing to inadequacies of manual systems to cope with Quality Management issues technology stepped in. Adoption of technology and computerized systems for Quality Management has seen progress in lock step with progress of Information and Communication technology (ICT) over the decades. In the 60s and 70s mainframe based computerized Quality Management solutions targeted statistical analysis and document control.

80s to 90s: Emergence of PCs, TQM, CAQ, QMS Software

In the 80s and 90s, advent of TQM (Total Quality Management) and PC (Personal Computer) brought forth revolutionary changes. We saw emergence of widespread Quality Management computerized solutions for document control, non-conformance reporting and corrective actions. Terms like CAQ (Computer Aided Quality), QMS (Quality Management System) Software were born then. During 80s and 90s DMS (Document Management System) and early ERPs (Enterprise Resource Planning) also served the needs of Quality Management.

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90s to Early 2000: EQMS Arrives

Internet and advancements in software development in 90s and early 2000s led to EQMS (Electronic Quality Management System). Often also referred to as Enterprise Quality Management System, EQMS is a software that deals comprehensively with all aspects of quality in the organization. It is typically designed with a cloud-based IT infrastructure and data model which facilitates cross functional communication and collaboration. EQMS provides centralized data management, improved accessibility and workflow automation. It also covers the crucial management of documents, compliance, feedback, supplier quality, audit, training and other quality related tasks.

Early 2000 to Date: AI Enabled EQMS

Today is overwhelmingly the age of ever evolving AI, Generative AI, and other 4IR (4th Industrial Revolution) technologies like Blockchain, IOT (Internet of Things) etc. AI is ubiquitous and the recently emerged Generative AI has commoditized AI. We can, with little thought and care, all use AI to be more productive and efficient individually and organizationally. Now the race is on to have the best AI enabled EQMS. AI embedded EQMS can have revolutionary impact on Quality Management.

More about AI (Artificial Intelligence)

AI is Old and Wide

AI is as old as computer science. Many wondered from early days

if machines could think. The quest to mimic human intelligence led to the coining of the term Artificial Intelligence by John McCarthy, preeminent American Computer and Cognitive scientist in Dartmouth conference in USA in 1956.

Human Intelligence v Artificial Intelligence

As it turned out this artificial intelligence or digital intelligence, residing currently on silicon substrate is pretty real, not artificial at all. It is undergoing explosive growth. Our human intelligence, real intelligence, in comparison, has a biological substrate. Human brain has billions of interconnected neurons transmitting electrical signals and chemical messenger. This allows us to think, learn, solve problems and be creative. We must not, however, underestimate or ignore but learn to cohabit with this powerful digital AI. This new digital 'species' has the potential to augment us as a human manifold.

Turing Test

Earlier in 1950 Alan Mathison Turing (1912-1954), Computer Scientist, Mathematician, Logician, Wartime Codebreaker, victim of prejudice, often called father of modern Computer Science proposed the famous Turing test for Artificial Intelligence. A machine will have passed the Turing test if its responses in conversations with humans are indistinguishable from that of a human response.

AI is all the Rage Today: ANI, AGI, ASI

AI has gone through its motions, hopes and frustrations, over the decades waxing and waning. But now AI is the rage and will be very significant in the foreseeable future. Currently most AI we see are narrow or weak AI adept at a specific task. AGI (Artificial General Intelligence) with human like general abilities is much talked about and debated. It is an aspiration for the near future. ASI (Artificial Super Intelligence), if and when achieved is touted to exceed human intelligence. AI in the form of sentient AGI or self-aware ASI can be scary

posing existential threat for humans. We need to collectively address this challenge and mitigate the risks it poses for the sake of humanity.

AI: Boon or Bane

Human's creative and innovative capacity can be boundless. Morales and values, however, always lag behind. It is imperative that human's unbridled, harmful to humanity ambition be kept in check. We must not be swayed by hubris, excessive pride and ambition. Hubris caused Greek mythology character Icarus (son of Daedalus, skilled craftsman and inventor) to plunge to his death when he flew too close to the

sun despite his father's warnings that wings made of feathers, strings and wax will not hold against excessive heat. AI can be a boon for humanity if we can steer it ethically, train it on good, unbiased data and in a pro humanity way.

Early Day AI: Expert Systems

Programming logic with 'if then else' or such constructs brought along well-crafted software solutions with decision making capability based on inputs. Software programmers from the early days of computing thus enabled computers to exhibit "intelligence" or decision-making capability. These were however not quite

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called AI. Attempts to build AI systems by codifying human expert's vast array of experience and reasoning led to what was called 'Expert Systems' in 80s. These early attempts at AI leading to 'Expert Systems' were attempts to represent through code human expertise, experiences and heuristics.

Symbolic AI with Explainability v Stochastic Non Symbolic AI

Codifying human expert's decision-making process, however, proved too laborious and challenging. This led to AI winter in 80s. These legacy AI were also called symbolic AI, symbols being the words,

numbers, logical operators or any other defined representations. Advantage of these symbolic AI was explainability of AI's reasoning. This explainability is not still there for results produced by our current self-learning AI, modeled on data and statistics, stochastic/probabilistic processes. There is also an aspiration now to move from this 'non-thinking' content generating Generative AI to 'thinking and understanding' objective driven AI, idea put forward by Yan LeCun, META's Chief Scientist in a META AI conference in London in Apr 2024.

Deep Learning (DL), Machine Learning (ML)

ANN (Artificial Neural Network) driven Deep Learning (DL), a subset of Machine Learning took center stage in last decade or so. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) based on transistors on silicon chips that can be turned on or off like a biological neuron were conceptualized as early as in 1940s. Inspired by our biological neural network (but not quite understanding how our 3 pound in weight, 20 watt brain with 86 billion neurons and 100 trillion synapses work) DL matured. DL made a paradigm shift of being able to learn, mainly unsupervised, when immersed in data.

Machine Discerns Patterns from Data

Task of codifying human expert's logical and heuristic reasoning proved quite impossible. Instead, machines with great computing power using powerful GPUs (Graphical Processing Units) were now fed with vast data to learn by themselves. Clever Learning algorithm and Deep Learning techniques consisting of input neuron layer, output neuron layer and many hidden neuron layers (hence coining of the word "Deep" in Deep Learning) in between would allow the computers to see patterns in data that is impossible for humans to see.

New paradigm: Tools learn and decide on their own

These patterns hidden in data allowed the machine to learn.

Everything in the world can potentially be expressed as functions. Machines have the capability to be function approximators using advanced stochastic/statistical techniques for curve fitting and hence be predictive. Thus, we now have tools which do not only take instructions from humans and execute but can learn by itself and decide to execute on their own. Imagine a hammer having enough "intelligence" to decide where to hammer a nail or a robot maintenance engineer deciding when to carry out maintenance or an AI agent (now emerging) deciding when to order and pay.

Generative AI Based on LLMs - Quite a Phenomenon

Also ushered in during mid 2010s Generative AI based on LLMs (Large Language Models) to generate new text, image,

audio, video given plain language inputs, called prompts, from the user. Generative AI used revolutionary frameworks like Transformer architecture from Google, with "Attention is all you need" feature for in context learning and detecting long range word dependencies. Hence the term GPT (Generative Pretrained transformer). These LLMs, fundamental models, are pretrained with data and use transformer architecture to generate new text, image, audio and video.

Chatbots: ChatGPT, Gemini, Poe: 'Einstein' in your Pocket

Recently a slew of continuously improving AI chatbots like ChatGPT from organization called Open AI, Gemini from Google and many others emerged. This has commoditized AI for everyone. ChatGPT and such other can write code that programmers used to write, write stories, draw pictures, compose music and make videos when prompted in plain language. These chatbots also can act as super knowledgeable personal assistant like an 'Einstein' in your pocket by ingesting all world knowledge to answer most of your questions.

Gen AI can Hallucinate but if well Trained can Boost QM

Generative AI or Gen AI do make mistakes and are not infallible. Hence the rise of prompt engineering with basically sequence of clear questions to lead them to give

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more sensible answers. Some of these Chatbots are free. More advanced versions work on a monthly subscription basis. There are multimodal model AIs which can take input from multiple modes i.e., text, image, audio and video like humans do and offer a more comprehensive understanding of the situation.

These Generative AI, on a constant path of improvement, can hugely boost Quality Management, if trained well with good data. Gen AI can give suggestions of how to comply with quality related regulations or suggest root causes for deviation from norm for root cause analysis.

Top Management must Own AI Function

Top Management Must be Fully Aware of AI's Capabilities

Just like ICT, AI function must be owned by top management and

guided properly. This will ensure overall sensible AI culture within the organization and resulting productivity gains through use of AI. Organizations must define clear objectives to integrate AI in their Quality Management and Quality Process. AI and Generative AI can take company performance to unprecedented heights only if it is well understood, applied with skill and wisdom, continuously monitored and managed to achieve the well-defined objectives.

Using AI for Quality Management and for Quality Process

Predictive Maintenance

Prevention is better than cure. Trained with right data AI can play a huge role in predictive maintenance for any organization. AI together with IOT (Internet of things) sensors can collect sensor data, analyze

data and predict defects before they occur. AI can also predict machine malfunctions before they occur. This predictive attribute of AI can be a game changer for any organization and is being used and improvised by large organizations like Amazon, Walmart and others. Amazon knows before you what you want to buy. Predictive algorithms let Amazon predict what a customer may want next month. Amazon then delivers the relevant goods to nearby warehouse in advance for prompt delivery.

Automated Visual Inspection

AI with computer vision and image processing ability can do automated visual inspections continuously of every process, do real time detection of defects and reporting of anomalies. Visual inspections can be through images and/or videos. Paint defects in cars or tears or imperfections in fabrics thus can be identified in time to significantly enhance quality control. Sam's club in Walmart is sprawled over 136,000 sqft of space and its shelves have about 6000 items. Robot Floor scrubbers in Sam's Club in Walmart are fitted with cameras which takes millions of pictures of items on shelf front and behind to monitor stock position or other item quality matters.

Data Driven Defect Analysis

AI enables Data driven defect analysis by analyzing vast

amounts of data. These data are acquired from various sources like inspections, sensor data and customer feedback. AI finds their correlation and then suggest root causes for defects or non-conformance. This helps businesses to pinpoint areas for improvement and implement targeted solutions to enhance overall quality. Thus, analyzing customer complaints alongside production data can be done by AI to identify correlation between specific production processes and quality issues raised by customer.

Non-conformance Management

AI excels by playing a huge role in non-conformance management. AI can flag and categorize non-conformance reports based on pre-defined criteria. This streamlines processes, ensures consistent documentation and allows for faster identification and resolution of quality problems.

Continuous Improvement

AI powers continuous improvement by suggesting adjustments to production parameters based on historical data and defect trends. This enables the organization to make informed decisions for continuous improvement to processes and optimize Quality Management. Keeping pace with technological advancements are a must for continuous improvement. Recently announced SORA (text to video model), GPT-4o (new flagship model that can

reason across audio, vision and text in real time) from Open AI, Gemini 1.5 Pro with advanced features from Google are a testament to the breathtaking progress in AI that we are witnessing.

Use of Generative AI in Particular for Quality Management and Quality Process

Benefits: Synthetic Data Generation

Real world data for, say, all kinds of defects can be limiting. Generative AI can generate images with simulated defects to train AI systems more comprehensively for visual inspection tasks. This is called synthetic data generation. Generative AI can therefore help create diverse scenarios for AI model to train on.

In software testing, for example, Generative AI can generate plethora of user interactions to ensure functionality under various stressed conditions. These automated test case generation helps identify potential weaknesses in products or processes that might be missed with traditional, pre-defined test cases.

Benefits: Visualizations of Potential Defects

In addition to simulating defects Generative AI can create visualizations of potential defects as a result of some possible weakness in the

process. For example, it can simulate how a type of structural weakness might manifest as a crack in a product under stress. This potential defect visualization and simulation can improve communication and collaboration between quality teams by providing a clearer understanding of quality issues.

Benefits: Root Cause Analysis

Root cause analysis is what Quality Managers always do to prevent recurrence of a problem. Generative AI can provide root cause analysis assistance by, say, hypothetically generating simulations of different process variations based on real data to pinpoint which ones might be causing a specific defect.

Benefits: Quality process optimization

Generative AI can assist in quality process optimization by optimizing quality control workflows. Gen AI identifies inefficiencies and suggest process improvements. Generative AI can weigh results of different quality workflow configurations to find the most efficient one for consistent quality.

Concerns

Generative AI relies on complex statistics and algorithm to generate content and has no real "understanding". There is talk about progression from Generative AI to Objective

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driven AI. They are essentially as good or as fair as the data they are trained on. That's not to take away the continually improving impressive results produced by these companies. One has only to follow the latest developments by leading companies like Open AI, Google, Microsoft, META and many others. Therefore, it is essential to look out for biases that may have crept into these models and remove them.

Explainability is another concern for Generative AI produced results. Generative AI uses mostly advanced stochastic/statistical techniques applied to data it is trained on to arrive at their responses. Improvements are happening in this direction by

combining Symbolic AI with non-Symbolic AI but one must be aware of this to exercise caution in accepting all that is suggested by Generative AI.

Conclusion

Use AI to Check AI

Certainly, AI with its increasing capabilities can be used to monitor its own mistakes. A case in point is GAN. GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks) uses two AIs, Generator and Discriminator. Discriminator spots whether image or video is real or created by Generator. Generator with iteration makes it like real and Discriminator with iteration gets better at spotting fakes.

No Technology is Infallible

No technology is without its pitfalls and its potential to cause harm. It is significantly more pronounced for AI. More the capabilities more the cause for concern. One must monitor a good worker so that he/she does not fall under bad influence. Likewise, AI must also be monitored for quality and unbiasedness of data, real or synthetic.

Cannot Outsource Alertness and Wisdom

Humans can outsource most things to AI but not their alertness and wisdom. Emerging multimodal conversational AI agents can take on multiple tasks, say, ordering, paying and more. This is all good. However, it is important for the top management and everyone else in an organization to understand that we cannot lose custody and control. AI tends to let humans slip into dangerous zone of trusting everything AI does and suggest. This is what we tend to do with a well performing outstanding employee also. Loosening oversight lets this well performing outstanding employee or AI to degrade and cause irreversible damage.

Clients Perception Towards CRM Practices Adopted by Banks and Insurance Companies: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Banks and insurance firms have been using CRM to understand diverse needs of clients and even trying to use the strategy of relationship building with the clients for attracting new clients and retaining existing clients. However, convincing clients for technology adoption to interact with bank and insurance is a major challenge. The objective of this research is to assess the progress made in the field of CRM in banking and insurance. This study aims to provide readers with a full understanding of the current dynamics and shed light on the current status of the literature pertaining to CRM in banking and in insurance sector. Furthermore, this study offers a comprehensive examination of the existing body of literature on CRM in banking and insurance through the utilization of bibliometric analysis. The Scopus database was utilized for data collecting in this study. The database utilized for this research consisted of a total of 418 documents spanning the years 1998 to 2023. This study examines the theoretical foundations, publication patterns, and citation trends within this field. Additionally, the study investigates commonly referenced journals, frequently employed research keywords, and the formation of research clusters. Based on an analysis conducted using Scopus, it has been determined that the domains of management and business research in the India

hold significant prominence in the examination of CRM studies. The analysis was conducted using VOSviewer, which revealed that research on CRM has exhibited inconsistent progress in scholarly publications.

Keywords

CRM; Insurance; Banks; Scopus; VOSviewer.

Introduction

The concept and strategies for Customer Relationship Management (CRM) emerged in early 90s where organizations recognized the importance of happy customers and their contribution in the success of business [1]. Success of banking sector is customer driven. CRM practices refer to strategies adopted by business organizations to understand the customers' expectations with the aim of maintaining good relations with them to ensure growth in overall sales. CRM was a much required strategy to be adopted by banks and insurance firm as all the customers here have individual constraints and individual requirements. These unique prerequisites rooted down the foundation of adopting CRM practices in banking and insurance sector [2]. Traditionally bank and insurance staffs were to manually record detail information about the customers (Deposit, history, reputation, loans availed etc). But now many software's are available in the market that significantly reduce the burden

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of bank staff by keeping centralized record of customers. These huge available data is then classified with the help of data mining techniques and finally used by management to take informed decisions. Role of ICT in bank automation and in insurance automation aims to provide flawless system of book-keeping, better customer services and smooth decision-making process [3]. Adoption of ICT in banking and insurance CRM services has assured great satisfaction among the customers. They are not limited by time and geographical location to get required information from the bank or from the insurance firms by using Laptop, smart phones and computer [4].

The primary objective of this study is to provide a thorough and inclusive examination of the existing body of literature and to address the existing knowledge gap by conducting a

bibliometric analysis of the current literature on CRM in banking and insurance. This analysis will examine the frequency of citations, volume of publications, years of publication, and journals of publication, contributing authors, contributing countries, and emerging trends and patterns in CRM research. The specific objective of this study is to detailed assessment on particular areas that warrant further inquiry, so providing valuable recommendations for prospective inquiries in this crucial field.

Literature Review

Researcher identified and analyzed CRM that compliance with the promised services and quality is the greatest tool of success which in return comes with a self-reported loyalty. It is a valuable and important predictor of consumer behavior and consumer purchasing

decisions. The trust in Islamic banks and Islamic insurance is a result of customer's belief that all Islamic banks are governed by rules of Shariah and are compliant to full fill them. This results in enormous growth of Islamic banks and Islamic insurance which rejoice comparatively more power and large market base consisting of customers who are strong supporter of religious laws and principles following organizations. Compliance somehow directly or indirectly impacts the attitude and intention [5]. Researchers identified and predicted that effective implementation and adoption of CRM strategies not only impacts the consumer trust in a positive manner but also increases their faith towards banks and accountability of the bank and insurance business. The major objective of their research is to make note of parameters responsible for measuring and impacting CRM reliability. As in today's time quantifying the efficiency of business process is key issue and problem faced by the organization in order to achieve an efficient and high performing outcomes [6].

Banks and insurance have been making use of different software that is specially designed to understand customer needs. Many banks and insurance companies gave developed special applications with which they are connected with the customers 24*7. Moreover, customer needs not to explain his problem/ doubts to

individual member attending his query. Automation processes as introduced with recent technology make sure that all detail information about customer requirement/expectations are recorded. One more benefit of interactions and transactions done through the Internet connectivity is that all the information is tracked and recorded in server logs that provide huge data which bank management uses to analyze and make business decisions. Databases can be rightly called as the soul of CRM. It is with the help of technology that all the information collected from customer is instantly filtered

and transformed in usable form [7] [8].

A researcher from India focused his work in the retail field and studied the customer Relationship management Strategies and practices adopted by the prominent Private Sector Banks in Kerala. The banks are effectively using these strategies for a sustainable growth rate and market competition. All these kinds of strategies practiced by banks are plays a significant role in the building of prosperous business and development of an economy [9]. Researcher analyzed that in majority of the statements employees are

holding a positive attitude towards customers queries with an exception in reply to the statements concerning the arrangement of another flight with immediate effect in case the booked flight gets delayed as in these kind of cases they usually reply in a neutral manner without denying in order to maintain relationships. But in actual grounds some employees recommends to employer Airline Company to consider the customer request in case of inconvenience to customer on airlines part in order to construct an everlasting bond of loyalty and convenient travel assurance with their passengers. Collectively the perception of

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employees will help to effectively implement the CRM practices for large customer base and good market value [10].

Methodology

The present work utilized data sourced from Scopus, a highly recognized and extensively employed comprehensive database among researchers for doing bibliometric analysis across diverse fields. The selection of Scopus as the database of choice was based on its status as one of the most extensive bibliographic resources in the diverse realm of scientific research. The research employed a methodology that involved utilizing a set of

keywords with cutoff symbols and Boolean operators. Specifically, the keywords "Customer Relationship Management" was combined with the terms "Banking or Insurance" using the Boolean operator "AND." The analysis was limited to the discipline of social science, computer science, business, and management. The indicated years of publication range from 1998 to 2023, with the search conducted in November 2023. The VOSviewer software was utilized by the researcher to conduct bibliometric analysis procedures, including citation analysis and the examination of co-occurrence patterns among key phrases and authors. Upon the completion of the file

extraction process, this software generates visual representations in the form of maps, facilitating the analysis of data derived from bibliographic references. These maps are designed to be easily comprehensible and interpretable.

Results and Discussion

This research investigates bibliometric variables, including the publication of manuscripts over time, the annual growth rate, and the types of documents, the source categories, the source titles, and the analysis of keywords. The Scopus database is utilized for data collection and analysis.

Number of Publications and Annual Growth Rate

Table-1: Publications and Year by Year Growth Rate

Year	No. of Published Articles	% (N=418)	Cumulative %	Growth Rate(%)
1998	01	0.24	0.24	-
2000	01	0.24	0.48	0.00
2001	01	0.24	0.72	0.00
2002	05	1.20	1.92	80.00
2003	05	1.20	3.12	0.00
2004	07	1.67	4.79	28.57
2005	08	1.91	6.70	12.50
2006	14	3.35	10.05	42.86
2007	15	3.59	13.64	06.67
2008	18	4.31	17.95	16.67
2009	16	3.83	21.78	- 12.50
2010	22	5.26	27.04	27.27
2011	22	5.26	32.30	0.00
2012	30	7.18	39.48	26.67
2013	21	5.02	44.50	- 42.86
2014	23	5.50	50.00	08.70
2015	19	4.55	54.55	- 21.05
2016	19	4.55	59.10	0.00
2017	26	6.22	65.32	26.92
2018	23	5.50	70.82	- 13.04
2019	30	7.18	78.00	23.33
2020	17	4.07	82.07	- 76.47
2021	22	5.26	87.33	22.73
2022	28	6.70	94.03	21.43
2023	25	5.97	100.00	- 12.00
Total	418	100.00		

The scholarly discourse on CRM in banking and Insurance had exhibited limited growth in the years leading up to its widespread recognition in 2006. Subsequently, there has been a significant increase in the quantity of published works on an annual basis. Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the entire quantity of papers published on the topic of CRM in banking and insurance, together with their respective proportions, cumulative percentages, and growth percentages. In the year 2019, there was a notable increase in the number of publications, as evidenced by Figure 1 and Table 1. Specifically, a significant proportion of these publications, amounting to 30 or 7.18% of the total CRM in banking and insurance publications, were observed. The projected increase in numbers for the year 2023 is attributed to the advent of Industry 4.0 and the ongoing technological advancements.

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Figure - 1: Publications on CRM in banking and insurance

Document Type

Figure - 2: Documents type of published articles

In addition to analyzing the documents, source types, and source titles, we also conducted an examination of the record retrieved from the database maintained by Scopus. The potential document types encompass data paper, books, book chapters, conference papers, reviews, and articles. Figure 2 displays the evaluation of document types conducted in this study. The predominant form of publishing in the field of CRM in banking and insurance is journal articles, accounting for 63.9% (267) of the total papers published. This is followed by conference papers, which constitute 24.9% (104) of the publications. Book chapter make up 5.7% (24) of the total, while review represent 2.2% (9) of the overall publications.

Source Type

This study has identified other kinds of source types in addition to the numerous document forms commonly used for articles on CRM in banking and insurance sector. Table 2 illustrates that, in contrast to proceedings and books, most of papers are published in journals.

Table-2: Source Type

Source Type	No. of published articles	% (N=418)
Journals	283	67.70
Conference Proceeding	84	20.10
Book Series	28	06.70
Book	21	05.02
Trade Journal	02	0.48
Total	418	100.00

Source Title

Table 3 presents a compilation of the primary source titles that have published articles pertaining to the topic of CRM in banking and insurance sector. The data presented in the table indicates that the journal "International Journal of Bank Marketing" has published the most number of publications pertaining to the topic of CRM in banking and insurance sector.

Table-3: Top Six Sources

Source Title	Total Publication	% (N-418)
International Journal of Bank Marketing	13	03.11
International Journal of Electronic Customer Relationship Management	12	02.87
International Journal of Business Innovation and Research	05	01.20
International Journal of Applied Business And Economic Research	05	01.20
International Journal of Economic Research	04	0.96
Lecture Notes In Computer Science Including Subseries Lecture Notes In Artificial Intelligence And Lecture Notes In Bioinformatics	04	0.96

Keywords Co-occurrence Analysis

The author's chosen keywords are analyzed using VOSviewer in order to identify their co-occurrences. The network representation of the authors' keywords, generated using VOSviewer, is depicted in Figure 3. The visual attributes, such as color, size of the arcs, font used and the width of the connecting lines, serve as indicators of the degree of association between the terms. Keywords that are frequently referenced together are indicated by the same color, suggesting a relationship between them. The diagram presented provides a visual representation of the interconnectedness and frequent co-occurrence of several elements within the realm of customer relationship management, including red-colored CRM, service quality, customer loyalty, insurance and banking sector.

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Figure - 3: Co-occurrence analysis of keywords

The analysis of keyword co-occurrence results in the formation of three distinct groups, each characterized by a varying number of keywords. Figure 3 illustrates the prominent association between the keyword "Customer Relationship Management," which exhibited the highest frequency, and the keywords "Public Relations," "Banking Industry," "Insurance Sector", "Service Quality," "Information Technology", and "Customer Satisfaction". The assertion posits that research on CRM in banking and insurance sector consistently pertains to the fields of quality service, customer loyalty, strategic planning, risk management and the utilization of technological advancements. Hence, it is anticipated that forthcoming researchers will prioritize these crucial terms while selecting contemporary customer relationship management as their area of study.

Table-4: Cluster Analysis

Cluster	Themes	Sub-Themes	Description
Cluster-1 Red	"Customer Relationship Management in banking and insurance sector"	CRM, Service Quality, Customer Loyalty, Customer Satisfaction, Banking & Insurance,	Customer Relationship Management (CRM) plays a pivotal role in influencing customer satisfaction within the banking & insurance sector. Insurance firms and banks have realized that nurturing strong, personalized relationships with customers is imperative for ensuring satisfaction and loyalty. CRM strategies are designed to cater to the diverse needs of customers across different regions and demographics. Banks that effectively leverage CRM to offer personalized, convenient, and secure services are likely to see higher levels of customer satisfaction and, subsequently, improved customer retention and loyalty [11] [12].

Cluster	Themes	Sub-Themes	Description
Cluster-2 Yellow	"Innovation and E-CRM"	E-Banking, Social Media, Online Assessment, Sustainable Development,	Innovation and E-CRM are symbiotically linked, revolutionizing how businesses engage and serve their clients. The fusion of innovative technologies within E-CRM systems has redefined client's interactions, offering a multifaceted approach to understanding and satisfying individual needs. These advancements include AI-driven predictive analysis, chatbots for real-time support, data analytics, enabling tailored & proactive customer service. The integration of innovative platforms & tools has streamlined communication and accessibility, allowing businesses to offer seamless, personalized experiences. The synergy between innovation and E-CRM is a driving force, shaping the future of customer relationships & service delivery [13] [14].
Cluster-3 Blue	"Classification of Customer and Risk Management"	Strategic Planning, Customer Churn, Segmentation, Decision Making, Competitive Advantage.	Customer classification involves categorizing clients based on their behavior, transaction volume, creditworthiness, and potential risks they pose to the institution. By stratifying customers into segments, banks and insurance can better allocate resources, customize services, and manage potential risks associated with each group. Risk management within these segments involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating various types of risks, such as credit risk, market risk, and operational risk. It involves employing tools and strategies to predict, prevent, and alleviate potential threats to the institution's stability and financial health. This classification and risk management process are dynamic, evolving alongside changing market dynamics, regulatory requirements, and customer behaviors to ensure the institution's sustained success and resilience [15] [16].

Contributing Organizations and Nations of CRM Publications

Writings on CRM in banking and insurance sector were contributed by 160 institutions from various nations. Figure 4 presents a visual representation of the leading ten institutions that have made significant contributions. The majority of scholarly investigations pertaining to the concept of CRM in banking and insurance sector have been conducted at the University of Tehran, University of Delhi and Islamic Azad University. The notion of CRM, while relatively recent, has garnered significant attention and interest among organizations. This is evidenced by a comprehensive analysis of 418 research documents sourced from 160 institutions, which indicates that a majority of organizations actively engage with and demonstrate awareness of the importance of CRM in banking and insurance.

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Figure - 4: Top 10 institutions contributed to publish on CRM in banking and insurance sector.

A total of 70 discrete nations made contributions to the body of literature on CRM in banking and insurance sector. India produced the most number of articles, totaling 97, with the China following closely behind with 49 pieces. Iran also contributed 49 articles, while United States, Taiwan and United Kingdom produced 32, 24, and 19 articles, respectively. This suggests that the issue of achieving a CRM in banking and insurance sector is increasingly recognized and that all nations are prepared to address this equilibrium.

Figure - 5: Top 10 countries contributed to publish on CRM in banking and insurance sector

Limitations and Future Direction of Research

First and main limitation is the potential for data overload and complexity. Banks and insurance firms accumulate vast amounts of customer data, and managing this information can become overwhelming. Ensuring the accuracy, security, and relevance of this data is a constant challenge. Additionally, integrating various systems and databases within a bank can be complex and time-consuming. Moreover, there might be resistance or difficulty in getting employees to fully embrace new CRM systems, leading to underutilization or improper implementation. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of customer preferences and behaviors means that CRM systems need to continuously adapt and evolve, posing a challenge in keeping up with the ever-changing customer landscape. Lastly, while CRM systems provide insights and data, interpreting and effectively utilizing this information to derive actionable strategies can be a significant challenge for banks and insurance institutions.

One potential future research direction in CRM within the banking sector could focus on the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning. Exploring how AI can enhance CRM capabilities to provide personalized, predictive, and real-time customer service would be valuable. Research could delve

into developing AI-driven algorithms that can analyze vast amounts of customer data to predict behaviors, preferences, and potential needs.

This predictive analysis could assist banks and insurance firms in offering more tailored and timely services to their customers, thereby improving customer satisfaction and loyalty. Additionally, studying the ethical implications of AI in CRM, such as data privacy, transparency, and customer consent, would be crucial for ensuring responsible implementation. Understanding how AI can be leveraged to enhance CRM without compromising on ethical considerations could be a promising avenue for future research in the banking as well as in the insurance sector.

Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the rising trends in CRM. The study employed descriptive analysis by doing an examination of Scopus analysis and bibliometric analysis. The utilization of bibliometric analysis was employed in order to ascertain the progression of scholarly inquiry pertaining to the concept of CRM in banking and insurance, utilizing co-occurrence data or keywords. The data set was obtained by utilizing Scopus metadata and subsequently analyzed using VOSviewers software. It may be inferred that during the course of two decades of study on CRM in

banking and insurance sector, there has been a consistent and progressive growth in the number and quality of research papers. The final mapping pertains to the advancement of CRM in banking and insurance sector through the utilization of co-occurrence analysis, specifically focusing on keywords [17]. The present mapping serves to establish a correlation between scientific principles and the prevailing groupings. In conclusion, this bibliometric analysis of research on CRM in banking and insurance sector offers a more comprehensive comprehension of the worldwide landscape, collaborative networks, and developing patterns in this particular domain. The results of this study provide a solid basis for future research efforts, delivering valuable insights to academics and professionals as they explore relevant topics and contribute to the existing body of knowledge on CRM in banking and insurance sector and CRM in other financial institutions.

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Impact of Amendments to IAS-1 Presentation of Financial Statements and New Securities & Exchanges Rules, 2020 on Auditor's Report and Financial Reporting

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Introduction

Back in February 2021, the International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) issued Disclosure of Accounting Policies which amended IAS-1 Presentation of Financial Statements (IAS-1) and IFRS Practice Statement 2 Making Materiality Judgements.

On the other hand, on 31 December 2020, Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) issued brand-new rules named as "Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020" by repealing its decades long rules "Securities and Exchange Rules, 1987".

The impact of the above amendment and replacements on the auditor's report and financial reporting will be discussed in the following section of this article.

Drivers to Write this Article

To contribute to knowledge sharing on recent updates and to help clear any confusion among professional accountants through ongoing discussions and guidance provided by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB).

Overview on the Amendments to IAS-1

Due to IASB's issuance of disclosure of accounting

policies back in 2021, Para 10, 114, 117 & 122 of IAS-1 was amended, para 117A to 117D of the said IAS was inserted and para 118 to 121 of the said IAS was deleted. These amendments revise the disclosure requirements in IAS-1 concerning accounting policies. Specifically, the term "significant accounting policies" has been replaced with "material accounting policy information." This information is deemed material if, when considered alongside other details in the financial statements, it could reasonably be expected to influence the decisions of primary users of general-purpose financial statements.

The amendments also update the supporting paragraphs in IAS-1, clarifying that accounting policy information related to immaterial transactions, events, or conditions is considered immaterial and does not need to be disclosed. Additionally, accounting policy information may be material due to the nature of the associated transactions, events, or conditions, even if the monetary amounts are insignificant. However, not all accounting policy information linked to material transactions, events, or conditions is necessarily material. The IASB has also provided guidance and examples to illustrate the use of the "four-step materiality process" outlined in IFRS Practice Statement 2.

The article was reviewed by
Sk. Ashik Iqbal FCA

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For quick reference, the extract of the most significant para(s) is given below:

Para	Before the amendments to IAS-1	After the amendments to IAS-1
10 (e)	notes, comprising significant accounting policies and other explanatory information;	notes, comprising material accounting policy information and other explanatory information;
114	Example of systematic ordering or grouping of the notes included significant accounting policies applied.	Example of systematic ordering or grouping of the notes includes material accounting policy information.
117	An entity shall disclose material accounting policy information. Accounting policy information is material if, when considered together with other information included in an entity's financial statements, it can reasonably be expected to influence decisions that the primary users of general-purpose financial statements make on the basis of those financial statements.	An entity shall disclose its significant accounting policies comprising: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The measurement basis (or bases) used in preparing the financial statements; and b. The other accounting policies used that are relevant to an understanding of the financial statements.
122	An entity shall disclose, along with its significant accounting policies or other notes, the judgements, apart from those involving estimations (see paragraph 125), that management has made in the process of applying the entity's accounting policies and that have the most significant effect on the amounts recognised in the financial statements.	An entity shall disclose, along with material accounting policy information or other notes, the judgements, apart from those involving estimations (see paragraph 125), that management has made in the process of applying the entity's accounting policies and that have the most significant effect on the amounts recognised in the financial statements.

To address the above change, back in November 2022, International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board's (IAASB) International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) working group published the 'Amendments to IAS-1 and the Impact on the ISAs: Disclosure of Material Accounting Policy Information'. Moreover, that change is also incorporated in the IAASB's handbook of 2022-2023 and 2023-2024. Per the said publication, 'where the circumstances are such that management of the entity is preparing the financial

statements in accordance with the IFRSs, including the amendments to IAS-1, the change to the illustrations of the independent auditor's reports on financial statements is as follows:

Independent Auditor's Report (Extract for Illustration Purposes)

To the Shareholders of ABC Company [or Other Appropriate Addressee]

Report on the Audit of the Financial Statements Opinion

We have audited the financial statements of ABC Company (the Company), which comprise the statement of financial position as at December 31, 20X1, and the statement of comprehensive income, statement of changes in equity and statement of cash flows for the year then ended, and notes to the financial statements, including material accounting policy information. In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly, in all material respects, (or give a true and fair view of) the financial position of the Company as at December 31,

20X1, and (of) its financial performance and its cash flows for the year then ended in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs)'.

Based on the above, the responsibility of the auditor to incorporate above changes in the audit report arise when management prepare the financial statements incorporating the amendments to IAS-1. So it's the role of the management to prepare the financial statements by incorporating the amendments as discussed.

Overview of the Relevant Laws and Regulations Concerning Impact on the Auditor's Report

As per proviso of rule 14(3) of BSEC's Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020:

an audit firm shall make the audit report in accordance with the international standards on auditing (ISA) applicable in Bangladesh ensuring the

provisions of the Companies Act, 1994, Financial Reporting Act 2015 or any other specification as directed by the Commission from time to time or any other relevant laws.

As per section 213(4) of the Companies Act, 1994, auditors are required to report the following matters in their report in the section "Report on other Legal and Regulatory Requirements"

a) they have obtained all the information and explanations which to the best of their knowledge and belief were necessary for the purposes of their audit and made due verification thereof;

b) in their opinion, proper books of accounts as required by law have been kept by the Company so far as it appeared from their examination of these books.

c) statements of financial position and statement of profit or loss and other

comprehensive income dealt with by the report are in agreement with the books of accounts and returns.

On the other hand, likewise the Companies Act, Financial Reporting Act, 2015 does not provide for similar reporting requirements for the statutory auditors.

Analysis of the relevant laws and regulations concerning auditor's reporting responsibilities:

In addition to the three reporting requirements in the preceding section, the statutory auditors were previously required, under the Securities and Exchange Rules, 1987, to report whether the expenditure incurred was for the purpose of the Company's business. The previous Rule also prescribed a format for auditor's reporting. However, this requirement has been removed in the updated Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020. However, the author noted that some external auditors continue to report on whether the expenditure incurred was for the purpose of the Company's business, despite this requirement being removed under the updated Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020.

According to the author, this does not necessarily suggest that these external auditors have inadequately audited the expenditure. It remains the responsibility of management and those charged with governance to ensure that all transactions serve a valid

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business purpose, including confirming that expenditures are made for the entity's business activities. Under the audit methodology outlined by the International Standards on Auditing (ISAs), statutory auditors may still test relevant assertions related to the company's expenditures during the audit period. However, in line with the new Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020, reporting on such expenditures in the "Report on Other Legal and Regulatory Requirements" section is no longer mandatory.

Unlike the Securities and Exchange Rules, 1987, the updated Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020 do not prescribe a specific format for the audit report. Therefore, considering the requirements of the Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020, along with the International Standards on Auditing, the following illustrative "Report on Other Legal and Regulatory Requirements" may be used.

Independent Auditor's Report (Extract for Illustration Purposes)

Report on other Legal and Regulatory Requirements

In accordance with the Companies Act, 1994, we also report the following:

a. We have obtained all the information and explanation

which to the best of our knowledge and belief were necessary for the purpose of our audit and made due verification thereof;

- b. In our opinion, proper books of account as required by law have been kept by the Company so far as it appeared from our examination of those books; and
- c. The Statement of Financial Position and Statement of Profit or Loss and Other Comprehensive Income dealt with by the report are in agreement with the books of accounts and returns.

Conclusion

Based on the above discussion, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB), as the regulatory body for the accounting profession (Members' Handbook, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh, 2023), may consider addressing these two issues to provide further guidance and reduce confusion among professional accountants. It is important to note that the above perspective reflects only the author's understanding and may differ from the views of others. To err on the side of caution, external auditors may also seek legal opinion to determine whether there is any regulatory

obligation to report on the business purpose of expenditures under the updated Securities and Exchange Rules, 2020. However, to promote consistency in reporting among practitioners, ICAB may consider issuing a clarification on the matter. To achieve this, ICAB may also engage in consultation with relevant other regulatory authorities such as the Financial Reporting Council and the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission.

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Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current: Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

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Abstract

The amendments to IAS-1 – Presentation of Financial Statements, to be applied retrospectively for financial reporting period beginning on or after 1 January 2024, modified the criteria of classifying liabilities with covenants as current or non-current. Key changes from the amendments include - (i) the removal of the requirement of an unconditional right, (ii) requirement of a right to defer settlement at the end of the reporting period, (iii) classification based on the right to defer settlement rather than intention, and (iv) classification without considering the potentiality of earlier settlement through conversion to equity for a liability which can be settled by transferring reporting entity's own equity instruments before maturity. The amendments also mandated additional disclosures for non-current liabilities that are subject to covenants requiring settlement within 12 months of the reporting date. The amendments standardized the approach of distinguishing between current and non-current liabilities. The amendments aim to address stakeholders' concern categorizing liabilities with covenants as current and non-current and improve the information that a company represents about its liabilities with covenants. The amendments may enhance the financial reporting quality and informed decision makings of stakeholders by introducing

more principle-based criteria for classifying liabilities as current or non-current, ensuring more accurate presentation of financial performance and metrics, and providing better insights into liabilities involving covenants. However, reporting entities may face many challenges in applying these criteria properly particularly in case of complex scenarios (financial structures or contractual arrangements), changes in management's intentions close to the reporting date, difference in local jurisdiction interpretations and requirements compared to IAS-1 requirements, and requirement of clear and comprehensive disclosures. Addressing these challenges requires designing of robust internal controls, exercising careful judgment, and ensuring clear communication.

Key Changes and Requirements

A. Background of Amendments

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) released narrow scoped amendments to Paragraphs 69 to 76 of IAS-1 – Presentation of Financial Statements on 23 January 2020. These amendments aimed to clarify the criteria for the classification of liabilities as either current or non-current. These clarified that the classification of liabilities as current or non-current should be based on rights prevalent at reporting date. After amendments paragraphs IAS-1.69(d) and IAS-1.73 both

Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current:

Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

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refer to the right to defer settlement and make it explicit that only rights in place at reporting date affect the classification of liabilities.

The impetus for these amendments originated from a request to the Board seeking clarification on the interaction between the classification principle in paragraph 69 and the requirements of Paragraph

Important Information

- **IAS-1 amendments clarify the criteria for determining whether to classify a liability as current or non-current.**
- **These amendments specify that the classification of liabilities as current or non-current should be based on rights prevalent at reporting date.**

73. Clarification was sought on scenarios where entities anticipate refinancing or extending an obligation under an existing loan facility. The initial proposal of amendments was made in Exposure Draft (ED) Annual Improvements IFRSs 2010-2012 Cycle (Proposed Amendments to IAS-1) (released in May 2012) (Deloitte, 2023). Later, these re-exposed interpedently in the ED Classification of Liabilities (released in February 2015). Over December 2015 – September 2019, the IASB accepted and discussed the feedbacks received on ED and finalized revisions. The Board issued Classification of Liabilities as Current or Non-current (Amendments to IAS-1) and fixed effective date for implementation as 1 January 2022. On 23 January 2020, the IASB issued Classification of

Liabilities as Current or Non-current (Amendments to IAS-1) providing a more general approach to the classification of liabilities under IAS-1 based on the contractual arrangements in place at the reporting date. The amendments had an effective date of 1 January 2022. In April 2020, IASB in it's a supplementary meeting to consider CVOID-19 related issues including timelines in implementing proposed amendments, decided to delay effective date of Classification of Liabilities as Current or Non-current (Amendments to IAS-1) by one year. In 31 October 2022, IASB published 'Non-current Liabilities with Covenants (Amendments to IAS-1) and fixed effective date of it as 1 January 2024 (Deloitte, 2023).

The Board claimed that

amendments will promote consistency in applying the requirements by helping companies to determine whether, in the statement of financial position, debt and other liabilities with an uncertain settlement date should be classified as current (due or potentially due to be settled within one year) or non-current.

The amendments include clarification of the classification requirements for debt a company might settle by converting it into own equity. The amendments clarify, not change, existing requirements, and so are not expected to affect companies' financial statements significantly. However, they could result in

companies reclassifying some liabilities from current to non-current, and vice versa.

B. Summary of Amendments

The following table presents the old terminology and the revised terminology outlined in IAS-1 Presentation of Financial Statements.

Table A: Old Terminology and Revised Terminology Outlined in IAS-1

Paragraph	IAS-1 (Old Version)	IAS-1 (Revised Version)
69(d)	It does not have an unconditional right to defer settlement of the liability for at least twelve months after the reporting period.	It does not have the right at the end of the reporting period to defer settlement of the liability for at least twelve months after the reporting period.
73	If an entity expects, and has the discretion, to refinance or roll over an obligation for at least twelve months after the reporting period under an existing loan facility, it classifies the obligation as non-current, even if it would otherwise be due within a shorter period. However, when refinancing or rolling over the obligation is not at the discretion of the entity (for example, there is no arrangement for refinancing), the entity does not consider the potential to refinance the obligation and classifies the obligation as current.	If an entity has the right, at the end of the reporting period, to roll over an obligation for at least twelve months after the reporting period under an existing loan facility, it classifies the obligation as non-current, even if it would otherwise be due within a shorter period. If the entity has no such right, the entity does not consider the potential to refinance the obligation and classifies the obligation as current.
76A		For the purpose of classifying a liability as current or non-current, settlement refers to a transfer to the counterparty that results in the extinguishment of the liability. The transfer could be of: (a) cash or other economic resources - for example, goods or services; or (b) the entity's own equity instruments, unless paragraph 76B applies.
76B	Terms of a liability, that could, at the option of the counterparty, result in its settlement by the issue of equity instruments do not affect its classification [69(d)].	Terms of a liability, that could, at the option of the counterparty, result in its settlement by the transfer of the entity's own equity instruments do not affect its classification as current or non-current if, applying IAS 32 Financial Instruments: Presentation, the entity classifies the option as an equity instrument, recognizing it separately from the liability as an equity component of a compound financial instrument.

Legend: ● Replaced ● Updated ● New Inclusion ● Transfer

Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current:

Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

Paragraphs 69(a) to (c)¹ remain unchanged. Accordingly, liabilities meeting any of the following criteria are categorized as current liabilities, while those not meeting these criteria are classified as non-current liabilities.

Main Changes

- The necessity for an 'unconditional' right has been removed.
- The right to defer settlement must exist at the end of the reporting period.
- Classification is determined by the right to defer settlement, not by intention.
- If an entity can settle a liability by transferring its equity instruments before maturity, classification is decided without considering the potentiality of earlier settlement through conversion to equity. This applies only if the conversion feature is categorized as equity under IAS 32.

C. Purpose of Amendments

The key purpose of the amendments to IAS-1 was to address stakeholders' concern regarding categorizing liabilities with covenants as current and non-current and improve the information that a company represents about its liabilities with covenants. The following points clarify how the intended purpose to be achieved:

- Align with Conceptual Framework: The amendments align the

Main Purpose of Amendments

- Address stakeholders' concern regarding categorizing liabilities with covenants as current and non-current and improve the information that a company represents about its liabilities with covenants.

classification criteria with the conceptual framework for financial reporting. The conceptual framework places a strong emphasis on accurately portraying an entity's financial status as of the reporting date, which includes classifying liabilities according to management's intention and the timing of their settlement(s). Through their alignment with the conceptual framework, the modifications facilitate financial reporting practice uniformity and reliability.

- Address timing issue: The amendments clarify the timing when refinancing arrangements can be considered for the classification of liabilities. This ensures that entities do not prematurely classify liabilities as non-current based on the expected

future refinancing that has not yet been finalized.

- Enhance relevant and reliability of financial statements: The modifications increase the financial statements' relevance and reliability by offering more precise information on the liabilities' classification. This helps to better understanding an entity's liquidity and financial health by users.

D. Effective Date of the Change

Reporting entities need to apply the amendments retrospectively for reporting periods beginning on or after 1 January 2024 (Deloitte, 2023). Earlier application is also permitted.

Effective Date

- From January 2024 retrospectively.

¹ Paragraphs 69(a) to (c): (a) If the entity expects to settle the liability within its normal operating cycle (e.g. trade payables), (b) If the entity holds the liability primarily for the purpose of trading, or (c) If the liability is due to be settled within 12 months after the reporting period.

For compliance, reporting entries will require to restate comparative statement of financial position at the end of the preceding period and opening statement of financial position at the beginning of the preceding period if the amendment results in material reclassification of liabilities in accordance with IAS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors. Table B shows the financial statements to be impacted by the first-time adoption of the amendment.

E. Key Facets of Applications of Amendments

I. Right to defer settlement

If any of the criteria of Paragraphs 69(a) to (c) is not satisfied, amended Paragraph 69(d) requires a liability to be classified as a non-current liability if the reporting entity has a right to defer settlement of the liability for at least twelve months after reporting date. The right no longer requires to be unconditional. An entity's right to defer settlement is rarely 'unconditional' because most loan arrangements contain conditions, or covenants, that it must meet in order to continue

Key Application Facets

- The right to defer settlement
- Classification based on rights to defer settlement rather than intention

Liabilities settled by transferring the entity's own equity instruments prior to maturity

- Additional disclosures regarding compliance with covenants after reporting date

deferring settlement beyond twelve months of reporting date.

New Paragraph 72A confirms that the right to defer settlement must have substance and must exist at the end of the reporting period. New Paragraph 72B provides clarification on the impact of covenants on an entity's ability to defer settlement (IFRS, 2022). If compliance with a covenant is required by the end of the reporting period, it determines whether the entity can defer settlement as of that date, regardless of when compliance is evaluated after

the reporting date. On the other hand, if compliance is required only after the reporting period, it does not influence the entity's right to defer settlement at the reporting period's end.

Example # 01: Effect on right to defer settlement at the end of reporting period

Entity X has a long-term bank loan repayable over five years. The bank reserves the right to demand immediate repayment if debt-to-equity ratio isn't maintained at each year-end. The year-end of the Entity X is 31 December 20X2.

The covenant's compliance is assessed based on audited financial statements finalized on 31 March 20X3. Entity X must adhere to the debt-to-equity ratio as of 31 December 20X2 despite verification occurring after year-end. If Entity X meets the ratio requirement by the end of 20X2, the bank loan will be classified as a non-current liability; if not, it will be classified as a current liability.

Table B: Financial Statements to be Impacted by the First Adoption of the Amendments

Reporting Date	First Time Application	Comparative Restatement	Opening Statement of Financial Position
31 December	31 December 2024	31 December 2023	1 January 2023
31 March	31 March 2025	31 March 2024	1 April 2023
30 June	30 June 2025	30 June 2024	1 July 2023
30 September	30 September 2025	30 September 2024	1 October 2023

Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current:

Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

Example # 02: No effect on right to defer settlement at the end of reporting period

Entity Y has a long-term bank loan repayable over five years. The loan is subject to some specific covenants including the requirement of maintaining working capital ratio of at least 1.00 at 31 December 20X2 and at least 1.10 at 30 June 20X3. The year-end of the Entity Y is 31 December 20X2.

As of 31 December 20X2, Entity Y's working capital ratio stands at 1.05. The management of the company anticipates to meet the required working capital ratio of 1.10 by 30 June 20X3. According to Paragraph 72B(b) of IAS-1, the compliance with 30 June 20X3 covenant is assessed after the reporting period ends, not at 31 December 20X2. Since the 30 June 20X3 covenant does not affect Entity Y's right to defer settlement as of 31 December 20X2, Entity Y classifies the liability related to the loan as a non-current liability at that date.

II. Classification based on rights to defer settlement rather than intention

Paragraph 73 of IAS-1 currently mandates that if an entity expects and has the option to refinance or extend an obligation under an existing loan agreement for at least

twelve months after the reporting date, it can classify the liability as non-current, regardless of its original due date within twelve months. The amendments eliminate the requirement to consider intention in this evaluation. Instead, classification is dependent solely on whether the entity has the contractual right to extend the obligation for at least twelve months under an existing loan agreement (KPMG, 2023).

Example # 3: Classification of liability based on rights to defer settlement rather than intention

Entity K has a loan arrangement with a bank to be expired on 31 March 20X3 while its fiscal year ends on 31 December 20X2. Entity K has option to extend this loan until 31 March 20X4. As of 31 December 20X2, Entity K plans to repay the loan on 31 March 20X3. The financial statements for the year ending 31 December 20X2 is authorized for issue on 30 April 20X3.

According to current IAS-1 requirements, Entity K categorizes the loan as a current liability because it does not intend to extend repayment beyond twelve months. However, recent amendments require that this loan be classified as long-term liability because the Entity K is entitled to defer payment for more than

12 months regardless of current intent. In this context, Entity K is actually going to repay the loan on 31 March 20X3, which is before the financial statements is approved for issue (30 April 20X3). This repayment should be disclosed as a non-adjusting subsequent event in Entity K's financial statements for 31 December 20X2.

III. Liabilities settled by transferring the entity's own equity instruments prior to maturity

Currently, a liability arising from a convertible note, that can be settled prior to maturity by issuing an entity's own equity instruments, is classified as current or non-current based on its terms rather than the possibility of earlier settlement via the issue of equity instruments (KPMG, 2023). For instance, if the convertible note is repayable in cash in three years but could be converted at any time into equity instruments, it is classified as a non-current liability. The amendments change this requirement. The classification of the instrument's conversion feature will now affect the current or non-current classification of the instrument. If the conversion feature is classified as a liability, the reporting entities must consider the early conversion option for current or non-current classification.

Chart A: Classification of Liabilities for Settlement with Own Shares

Example # 4: Liabilities to be settled in exchange of entity's own equity instruments prior to maturity

Entity M has a Currency 5 Million Note Payable that includes a conversion option allowing conversion into 5 million ordinary shares of the company at any time during the note's term. The Note is repayable with interest in five years if not converted.

The conversion feature of the note is categorized as a derivative financial liability rather than an equity instrument under IAS 32 Financial Instruments: Presentation. Therefore, the presence of the early conversion option influences the classification of the financial liability. Because the note can be converted into shares at any time, the debt component of the note is classified as a current liability.

IV. Additional disclosures regarding compliance with covenants after reporting date

The amendment requires more disclosure about liabilities classified as non-current for a situation when right to defer settlement is subject to the compliance of loan covenants in the next twelve months. Reporting entities should disclose the followings:

- Nature of the covenants
- Timing of the requirement to comply with the covenants
- Carrying amount of liabilities affected by the covenants
- Facts and circumstances, if any, that indicate that the entity may have difficulty to comply with the covenants

- Facts, if applicable, that the entity would not have complied with the covenants if they were to be assessed for compliance based on the entity's circumstances at reporting date.

Impact of Amendment in Financial Reporting and Analysis

The amendments to IAS-1 regarding the classification of liabilities as current or non-current have several notable impacts on financial

Impact of Amendment in Financial Reporting and Analysis

- Amendments provided clearer guidelines on classifying liabilities as current or non-current. Liabilities are now be classified following a more principles-based approach considering the entity's rights at the end of the reporting period.
- Amendments promoted proper classification of liabilities that in-turn ensures that financial ratios i.e. current ratio and working capital will accurately reflect an entity's short-term liquidity and operational efficiency.
- Amendments mandated improved disclosure practices particularly concerning liabilities contingent upon loan covenants.

Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current:

Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

reporting and analysis. These are discussed below:

(i) Improved clarity and transparency: The amendments to IAS-1 provided clearer guidelines on the criteria for classifying liabilities as current or non-current. Previously, the classification was primarily based on the timing of settlement (i.e., whether the liability was due within 12 months after the reporting period). Now, the revised standard requires reporting entities to assess their rights at the end of the reporting period. If the entity has a right to defer settlement of the liability for at least 12 months after the reporting period, it may classify the liability as non-current even if settlement is due within 12 months. Besides the contractual terms, management's intentions regarding the settlement of

liabilities also now be undertaken into consideration. If a liability is due within 12 months, but management intends to refinance or roll over the obligation on a long-term basis, it might be classified as non-current.

(ii) Improved presentation of financial performance and metrics: The categorization of liabilities has significant impact on the presentation of financial position and financial ratios of the reporting entities. More accurate classification under the revised guidelines will ensure that financial ratios such as current ratio (total current assets ÷ total current liabilities) and working capital (total current assets - total current liabilities) provide better insights into an entity's short-term liquidity and operational efficiency.

(iii) Improved disclosure: The amendments require more detailed disclosure of non-current liabilities with covenants. By disclosing the nature of covenants, timing of compliance requirements, carrying amount of liabilities affected, and potential difficulties or circumstances indicating non-compliance risks (if any), reporting entities provide stakeholders with crucial insights into the company's financial health and risk management practices. This enhanced disclosure will enable users of financial statements to better assess the reporting entities' liquidity position in various scenarios including potential covenant breaches.

Potential Challenges in Implementation and Compliance

While the amendments to IAS-1 regarding the classification of liabilities aim to provide clearer guidance, their implementation poses several potential challenges for reporting entities.

First significant challenge can be the interpretation and application of the classification criteria themselves. Even the amendments aim to standardize and clarify the criteria, there can still be room for interpretation especially in cases involving complex financial structures or contractual arrangements. For instance, determining whether a

Challenges in Implementation and Compliance

- Classification of liabilities as current or non-current can be subjective especially for complex financial structures or contracts.
- Changes in management's intentions or strategic decisions near the reporting date can complicate classification.
- Entities operating internationally or across multiple jurisdictions may encounter challenges aligning their classification practices with local accounting standards or regulations.
- Amendments to accounting standards often require entities to enhance their disclosure practices.

liability should be classified as current or non-current may be hinged on some nuanced factors i.e. entity's ability and intent to refinance, renegotiate terms, convert debt into equity within the next twelve months after the reporting date etc.. In such situations, detailed analyses and judgements will be required which can vary among entities or even among accounting professionals within the same entity.

Challenge can arise from the changes in management's intentions or strategic decisions

occurred close to the reporting date. For illustration, if management plans to refinance a liability shortly after the reporting date but did not formalize this intention, determining the appropriate classification can be very challenging. The timing and specification of such intentions can significantly affect classification decision and potentially can lead to inconsistencies and/or delays in financial statements finalization.

Reporting entities, if operate in multiple jurisdictions, may face challenges in the alignment of their classification practices as per IAS-1 with those of local accounting standards or regulations. While IAS-1 provides a global framework, local interpretations and requirements can sometimes differ. If requirements of IAS-1 and local accounting standards or regulations become different, additional disclosures to reconcile the discrepancies will be required.

Finally, reporting entities may face challenges to provide additional disclosures for non-current liabilities with covenants as per the amendments. It may be difficult and time worthy to gather necessary information that will justify the classification judgments made. Unclear and lack of sufficient disclosures can compromise to the transparency in financial reporting.

Recommendations to Address Challenges in Implementation and Compliance

Addressing the challenges associated with implementing the amendments to IAS-1 regarding the classification of liabilities as current or non-current demands a systematic approach centered around robust internal controls, careful judgment, and clear communication.

Reporting entities require to establish robust internal controls to ensure uniform and consistent application classification criteria across different scenarios and reporting periods. This involves with developing clear policies

Summary of Recommendations

- Robust internal controls help to maintain rigorous standards in financial reporting and ensure that classification criteria are applied as per amended requirements of IAS-1.
- Informed judgment helps to address complexities and guide to accurate classification decisions.
- Clear communication through enhanced disclosures fosters stakeholder trust by providing clarity on how liabilities are classified and their impact on financial reporting.

Amendments to Guideline for Categorizing Liabilities as Current or Non-current:

Key Changes, Requirements and Implications

and procedures that align with the amended classification criteria.

Reporting entities require to exercise careful judgments in navigating complex situations where uncertainties exist. Training and educating accounting teams on the nuances of the amended standards can enhance their ability to exercise independent judgments. Additionally, seeking guidance from external experts can provide valuable insights and validation in challenging cases.

Finally reporting entities should focus on clear communication for ensuring accurate and transparent financial reporting. Entities should enhance disclosures related to liability classification in their financial statements. These disclosures should articulate the rationales behind classification decisions, highlight any significant uncertainties or assumptions, and provide insights of the impact of classification on financial position and metrics.

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International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1): Is Bangladesh Ready to Adopt this Standard in Firm Level

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Background of the Development of ISQM

In 2005, the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB) introduced the International Standard on Quality Control 1 (ISQC 1). It was formulated to help audit firms to organize and maintain quality control procedures. However, over time, it became clear that ISQC 1's old-fashioned, reactive approach that didn't fit well with the modern businesses. This was due to various reasons, like its failure to focus on reducing risks and its outdated "tick-box" compliance method. In response to these challenges, the IAASB developed the International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1). ISQM 1 encourages audit teams to take a more proactive and independent approach to audits. It sets out guidelines to ensure audits meet international standards for quality and consistency. Since December 2022, ISQM 1 has replaced ISQC 1 as the standard that audit firms must follow. This shift was prompted by various quality issues. Now, firms must adapt to the complexities of ISQM 1, alongside ISQM 2 and revised ISA 220 standards. Among these changes, ISQM 1 has the most significant impact on how firms conduct their work. It's crucial for professionals involved in audits or financial statement reviews to understand and implement these new standards effectively.

What is Audit Quality and why it Matters?

Audit Quality

Audit quality refers to the excellence in audits ensuring financial statement accuracy. Key aspects, per the Center for Audit Quality (CAQ), are auditor expertise and independence, and fostering trust. The IAASB emphasizes a conducive environment for consistent high-quality audits, involving ethics, skills, and adherence to standards. This entails rigorous processes, timely reporting, and stakeholder engagement. In essence, audit quality hinges on expertise, independence, adherence to standards, and effective communication, upholding financial reporting integrity.

Why Audit Quality Matters

The importance of audit quality is paramount for auditors, directly reducing audit risk and ensuring appropriate opinions. Key points on its significance include:

- ❖ Audit quality is the foundation for reducing risk and ensuring accurate financial reporting.
- ❖ Regulatory oversight is crucial for promoting quality audits, despite firms' efforts.
- ❖ Audit firms face pressures like tight deadlines and ethical dilemmas, challenging quality maintenance.

**International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1):
Is Bangladesh Ready to Adopt this Standard in Firm Level**

- ❖ Quality audits go beyond compliance, fostering trust, transparency, economic stability, and investor confidence.
- ❖ Quality audit protects public interest.
- ❖ Quality audits help prevent financial scandals, protecting investors and market credibility.
- ❖ Upholding audit quality is a professional obligation and a global economic safeguard.
- ❖ Ensuring audit quality is vital for upholding the integrity of the global economy.

Thus, maintaining audit quality is not just a professional obligation but also safeguards the local and global economy's integrity.

Standards for Audit Quality

The International Forum of Independent Audit Regulators (IFIAR) stresses the importance of robust quality control systems in bolstering audit quality, a focus reflected in inspection programs. Concerns about inconsistent inspection findings led to the introduction of new standards by the IAASB in December 2020. ISQM-1 aim to modernize quality management by emphasizing monitoring, remediation, and integration of quality into corporate culture. Similarly, the Auditing Standards Board (ASB) issued comparable standard in June 2022 which was ISQM-2.

ISQM-1: The Quality Management System of the Firm (ISQM 1)

ISQM-1 improves firms' quality management systems for audits, financial statement reviews, and other assurance services by promoting a robust and proactive approach. It encourages firms to create customized systems aligned with their context and engagements. ISQM-1 replaces ISQC-1, which focused on quality control for similar services.

The primary aim of ISQM-1 is for firms to establish, execute, and sustain a quality management system for their audit, review, or other assurance engagements. This system should provide the firm with reasonable assurance that:

- a) The firm and its personnel adhere to professional standards, legal, and regulatory requirements, and conduct engagements accordingly.
- b) Reports issued by the firm or engagement partners are suitable for the given circumstances.

A quality management system operates continuously and adaptively, responding to changes in the firm's environment and engagements.

Key Changes Overview

- ❖ Shift from quality control to emphasizing quality management.
- ❖ Encouragement to customize the system of quality management (SOQM) according to the

firm's nature and engagement circumstances.

- ❖ Adoption of an integrated and proactive approach.
- ❖ Focus on achieving quality objectives by identifying and responding to quality risks.
- ❖ Strengthened firm governance and leadership, with increased leadership responsibilities.
- ❖ Modernization, including leveraging technology, networks, and external service providers.
- ❖ Improved information dissemination and communication.
- ❖ Implementation of proactive monitoring and efficient remediation of

deficiencies, with support provided.

Applicability

All firms conducting any of the following types of engagements:

- ❖ Audit or review of financial statements
- ❖ Other assurance engagements, such as extended external reporting or reports on controls at service organizations
- ❖ Engagements related to services, like compilations and agreed-upon procedures

Structure & Components

Standard Comprises:

- ❖ Eight components

- ❖ Other requirements addressing specific topics

Components address:

- ❖ Processes
- ❖ Environment in which the system operates
- ❖ What is needed to operate the system
- ❖ Specific topics fundamental for engagement performance

ISQM-2: Engagement Quality Reviews

Objective and Scope of the standard: ISQM 2 defines the scope of engagements requiring an Engagement Quality (EQ) review and outlines procedures for appointing and assessing the eligibility of EQ reviewers. It also details their responsibilities in conducting and documenting the EQ review process.

ISQM 1: Specified responses include EQ reviews and selection of engagements for EQ review:

- ❖ Audits of listed entities;
- ❖ Required by law/regulations (e.g., PIE);
- ❖ Firm determines that EQ review is an appropriate response to address one or more quality risk(s)

**International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1):
Is Bangladesh Ready to Adopt this Standard in Firm Level**

If EQ is required?	ISQM 2 Applies ➤ Appointment/eligibility ➤ Performance ➤ Documentation
If EQ is not required?	ISQM 2 does not applies

<p>Eligibility Requirements for EQ Reviewers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Threats to objectivity: 2-Year cooling-off period for an engagement partner to serve as EQ reviewer ❖ Sufficient time to perform EQ review ❖ Permitted use of qualified external EQ reviewers and assistants ❖ Action when eligibility of EQ reviewer is impaired <p>Performance of EQ Reviews:</p> <p>Focus on significant matters and significant judgment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Involvement of EQ reviewer at appropriate points in time throughout engagement ❖ Stand-back requirement: whether performance requirements of ISQM 2 have been fulfilled ❖ Engagement partner precluded from dating engagement report until notification of completion from EQ reviewer <p>Objective of the Firm</p> <p>By appointing a qualified EQ reviewer, the firm aims to conduct an impartial</p>	<p>assessment of the significant judgments made by the engagement team and the resulting conclusions.</p> <p>Effective Date</p> <p>ISQM-2 is applicable to all engagements mandating an EQ review as per ISQM-1. It became effective for periods starting on or after December 15, 2023.</p> <p>How International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM-1) be Implemented in Firm Level</p> <p>Firm's Risk Assessment Process</p> <p>Firm's risk assessment process comprises to-</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Establish quality objectives b) Identify and assess quality risks c) Design and implement responses d) Identify information indicating need to add/modify quality objectives, quality risks or responses <p>a. Quality objectives</p> <p>Establish quality objectives:</p>
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- ❖ Define quality objectives within the components.
 - ❖ Identify supplementary quality objectives required to fulfill the goals of the ISQM.
 - Based on firm judgment
- Optional: Establish sub-objectives
- ❖ May enhance identification and assessment of quality risks and designing responses

A partially established quality objective constitutes a deficiency unless it's deemed irrelevant to the firm.

b. Quality Risk

Understand conditions, events, circumstances, actions or inactions

- ❖ Take into account (i.e., think about) how they may adversely affect the achievement of the quality objectives
- ❖ Identify whether there are risks that are quality risks

ISQM 1 specifies conditions, events, circumstances, actions or inactions

- ❖ ISQM 1 is not complete (i.e., there may be others)
- ❖ Not all are relevant to every quality objective

c. Responses

- ❖ Mitigate possibility of quality risk occurring, so

quality objectives are achieved

- ❖ Design and implement responses to address quality risks
 - Based on, and responsive to, the reasons for the assessments given to the quality risks
 - How, and the degree to which, the conditions, events, circumstances actions or inactions affect the quality objectives
 - The possible occurrence of the quality risks
- ❖ Responses specified in ISQM 1: Not comprehensive and do not fully address all quality risks

d. Addition and modification

Proactive approach to quality management - respond to:

- ❖ Changes in the nature and circumstances of the firm or its engagements
 - Required to have policies or procedures to identify information that indicates the need for changes to quality objectives, quality risks or responses
 - Information relates to changes in the nature and circumstances of the firm or its engagements
- ❖ Remedial actions to address deficiencies
 - Monitoring and remediation process highlights deficiencies

The scalability of the firm's risk assessment process hinges on several factors. Firstly, it relies on exercising professional judgment to adapt to varying contexts. Secondly, the establishment of quality

Challenges for Audit Firms in Adjusting to the New Standard

Transitioning to a new standard such as ISQM 1 can pose several challenges for audit firms:

- a) **Complexity of Compliance and Resource Allocation:** Understanding and adhering to all requirements while ensuring full compliance can be complex. Smaller firms may face difficulties in allocating sufficient resources for this purpose.
- b) **Cultural Shift and Training Investments:** Firms may need to alter their mindset and practices to prioritize risk management and quality control over mere procedural compliance. This might necessitate significant investments in training.

- c) **Documentation Requirements:** Audit firms are required to maintain extensive records to demonstrate compliance, which can be labor-intensive and may necessitate the implementation of new documentation systems.
- d) **Effective Monitoring:** Establishing monitoring and review systems can be time-consuming, particularly for larger firms with multiple engagements.
- e) **Integration with Existing Systems:** The transition period to fully implement ISQM 1 can be demanding. Firms may need to modify existing systems to ensure seamless integration across the organization.
- f) **Navigating Industry-Specific Requirements and**

Global Variations: Different regions or countries may have specific regulations, and certain industries or sectors may present unique audit challenges and requirements that firms must navigate.

In Bangladesh context the following will be challenges for mostly small and medium firm

- a) Practitioner is not aware about this Standard.
- b) Incomplete or incorrect assessments due to lack of awareness or misunderstanding
- c) Leadership responsibilities is not clearly defined in the small and medium firm and Practitioner is not read the full standard issued.
- d) Absence of HR department and no policy for Human resources.
- e) Absence of written policy regarding the quality control of firm engagement.
- f) Absence of monitoring the quality at firm level and engagement level before issuing the report
- g) Employees training is not performed at firm level.
- h) Firms sometimes do not maintain standard working paper files
- i) Firms sometimes do not maintain audit planning and risk assessment documentation.

**International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1):
Is Bangladesh Ready to Adopt this Standard in Firm Level**

j) In Partnership firm absence of firmwide coordination.

Recommended Measures to Meet up the Challenges

Based on the challenges outlined for audit firms adjusting to the new standard ISQM-1, here are some recommendations:

- a) **Proactive Adoption:** Audit firms should embrace ISQM-1 early to ensure compliance by the December 15, 2024 deadline.
- b) **Training and Workshops:** Increase workshops and training for smaller firms to aid in implementing new standards effectively.
- c) **Templates and Tools:** ICAB can develop templates and standardized documentation to support firms in establishing quality management systems.

d) **Quality Inspection Process by ICAB:** Integrate ISQM-1 components into inspection checklists for regular evaluation of quality management systems.

e) **Public Interest Entities (PIE) and ISQM-2:** FRC should redefine PIEs or clarify ISQM-2 application to avoid excessive review burdens.

f) **Periodic Inspections:** Regulators must ensure effective implementation of new standards through ongoing inspections.

g) **Transparency Reports:** Mandate transparency reports for listed entity auditors to enhance quality assurance and public trust.

h) **Audit Fee Structure:** Audit fee is directly related to the quality of audit hence existing audit fee regime should be revisited or policy decisions taken to enhance

the effectiveness of implementation of the related Guideline issued by the Institute and initiate dialogue with stakeholders

Benefits of Implementing IQSM for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

By implementing this process, a numerous advantages have offer for small and medium-sized firms, including:

- a) **Proactive Quality Management:** ISQM 1 emphasizes identifying and addressing root causes of deficiencies, reducing risks over time and lowering insurance premiums.
- b) **Clear and Achievable Goals:** The standard sets clear quality objectives at the firm level, ensuring consistent engagement quality and simplifying goal-setting for small and medium firms.
- c) **Scalability and Flexibility:** ISQM 1's objective-based approach allows firms to tailor responses to their specific risks, integrating them seamlessly into existing management systems.
- d) **Continuous Improvement:** Regular risk assessments help firms identify and address weaknesses, leading to more efficient engagements, better client relations, and enhanced profitability.

- e) **Focused Responses:** Understanding the firm's specific circumstances enables precise risk assessments, allowing for targeted training and resource planning to ensure the right people are available for the right tasks at the right time.
- f) **Enhanced Communication and Quality Culture:** ISQM 1 fosters honest communication and feedback, improving documentation and embedding quality management into all aspects of the firm's operations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the adoption of the International Standard on Quality Management (ISQM), particularly ISQM-1, represents a significant milestone in the evolution of audit standards and practices. Through our discussion, we have identified various challenges that audit firms may encounter in adjusting to this new standard, ranging from compliance complexity to cultural shifts and integration with existing systems. However, it's crucial to recognize the importance of

ISQM in enhancing the quality and integrity of audit engagements. ISQM promotes a risk-based approach, fosters a culture of quality and ethical conduct, and emphasizes continuous improvement in quality management systems. By addressing these challenges and embracing the principles of ISQM, audit firms can strengthen their capacity to deliver high-quality audit services, instilling confidence and trust among stakeholders in financial reporting and assurance processes. As we navigate through the transition to ISQM, it is imperative for audit firms to remain vigilant, adaptable, and committed to upholding the highest standards of professionalism and quality in their practices.

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**International Standard on Quality Management 1 (ISQM 1):
Is Bangladesh Ready to Adopt this Standard in Firm Level**

Annexure-A

Acceptance and Continuance of Client Relationships and Specific Engagements

Quality Objective No.	Quality Objective	Possible Quality Risks	Possible Response/Control to mitigate those QR			
			Control name	Control description	Control owner	Frequency of control application
1	(i) Information obtained about the nature and circumstances of the engagement and the integrity and ethical values of the client (including management, and, when appropriate, those charged with governance) that is sufficient to support such judgments; and (Ref: Para. A67-A71) (ii) The firm's ability to perform the engagement in accordance with professional standards and applicable legal and regulatory requirements. (Ref: Para. A72)	Risk-1 Adequate information about new or continuing clients and engagements is not obtained and considered on a timely basis.	5.1 Acceptance and continuance of client relationships and specific engagements policy statement 5.2 Client screening questions 5.3 New client form 5.5 New client acceptance checklist 5.6 Client retention checklist	For each new engagement acceptance procedures particularly obtaining information about the client, completing new client questioner, checking of any ethical conflict, regulatory compliance like Copy of AGM, Appointment letter, professional clearance letter, client evaluation form etc. duly done.	Engagement Partner	Recurring
Human	Resources					
2	Competence & capabilities of HR: (able to) Consistently perform quality engagements, including having knowledge or experience relevant to the engagements the firm performs; or Perform activities or carry out responsibilities in relation to the operation of the firm's system of quality management.	Risk-1: Recruitment policies and processes are unclear or inappropriately documented to recruit personnel that have the knowledge and experience relevant to the engagements the firm performs.	Resources policy statement Candidate interview and evaluation checklist new staff orientation checklist	Firm has HR policy under which engagement Manager with approval from line partner send requisition to the HR for staff recruitment along with job description. Accordingly, HR initiates the recruitment process and completes the recruitment as per HR policy.		

Board Composition and Financial Stability of Firms: Emerging Economy Context

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Abstract

This paper aims to investigate the impact of board composition on financial stability in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh. A longitudinal cross-sectional panel data set of 17 Bangladeshi food and allied companies from 2012 to 2023 was analyzed using several statistical approaches, including multiple discriminant regression. The findings imply that financial stability is influenced by firm governance level (i.e. board size, board independence, board diversity, board activity, audit committee size), and firm-level factors (i.e. Return of equity, and solvency). The study's findings can have significant practical implications for creditors, governments, regulators, and other stakeholders to create reliable credence about a company's financial condition.

Keywords

Board composition, Board independence, Financial stability, Panel data.

Introduction

Since financial instability directly affects the company, shareholders, and ultimately the general public, it is a stimulating topic to pay attention to. According to Andrade and Kaplan (1998), a company is financially unstable if it is unable to pay its debts to third parties or if it is trying to restructure debt due to difficulties in making payments (Ali & Nasir,

2018). According to Altman, Iwanicz-Drozowska, Laitinen, and Suvas (2017), several different factors might lead to financial agony, including external economic shocks, internal mismanagement, or a combination of the two. As a means of navigating and mitigating the risks connected with financial instability, the governing body (corporate governance) plays a critical role in tackling these difficulties. In emerging markets, company collapses are frequent. In light of this, the World Bank (WB), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and numerous other international organizations that care about the social and economic advancement of all countries, along with the policy-making bodies of numerous other nations, have taken up the task of developing better governance standards (Ferdous, 2018). Corporate governance (CG), according to Wesa and Otinga (2018), is the body of policies and guidelines that guarantee managers apply the concepts of value-based management. This study attempts to investigate the relationship between board composition (corporate governance) and financial instability using extensive literature research and empirical investigation. The study also aims to investigate how board structure, diversity, independence, and activity have a role in either exacerbating or lessening financial difficulty.

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The results of this study will be extremely helpful in understanding how the composition of a board influences the management or prevention of financial difficulty, which is a crucial topic for businesses that operate in unstable and resource-constrained markets. Through the identification of critical governance elements that impact financial health, such as board independence, diversity, and activity, the study can assist investors, business leaders, and legislators in developing more efficient governance procedures.

Food Industry in Bangladesh

Bangladesh's manufacturing sector, particularly the food industry, is quickly growing. All firms want to improve their

market competitiveness (Hossain, Kabir, & Mahub, 2019). Increasing the number of food processing enterprises is crucial for all nations. This sector earns US \$ 422.28 million in the financial year 2022-23 (EBP, 2023). The food processing industry produces a variety of commodities, including frozen food, tea, vegetables, cereals, bakery and confectionary, fruits and vegetables, dairy, carbonated beverages, non-carbonated fruit juices, drinks, and other food items (Sarkar, Anjum, & Khan, 2017). After meeting local demand, processed items are sold to 70 countries worldwide.

Corporate Governance and Financial Stability

Altman (1968) found that legal financial troubles are equivalent to bankruptcy and must be

liquidated. This is consistent with findings from Simanjuntak, Krist, and Aminah (2017). The presence of financial crisis that leads to bankruptcy has an impact on the role of governance in the organization, particularly the control function. There is a link between corporate governance structure and financial troubles since financial difficulties are not independent phenomena. Several earlier research found that firm failure was directly tied to the CEO, board of directors, and members of upper management. A similar study has been conducted in industrialized countries (Armstrong, Guay, and Weber, 2010); (Gillani, Ramakrishnan, Raza, and Ahmad 2018); (Bayar, Huseynov, and Sardarli 2018). This study employs several proxies to describe the role of corporate governance in managers' control functions, including board size, board activity, and independence.

Literature Review

Financial health reveals vulnerabilities in governance frameworks, particularly in board composition, managerial oversight, and shareholder protection. Table 1 below provides an overview of the publications that were examined to carry out the investigation.

Table 1: Summary of the reviewed literature

SL.	Name of Author and Year	Country, period, & Method	Findings
1.	Handriani, Ghozali, and Hersugodo (2021)	Indonesia, 2010 to 2018, Multiple regression	It was discovered that institutional ownership, business size, profitability, and board independence were all beneficial criteria in the quest to avoid a financial collapse. Meanwhile, the board size variable showed a negligible positive connection.
2.	Meeampol et al. (2014)	Thailand, 2010 and 2011, EM-Score model	The investigation shows that the Emerging Market Z-score model and the Z-score model may accurately identify potential bankruptcy. Furthermore, they are more effective with two years of information compared to one year.
3.	Younas, UdDin, Awan, and Khan (2021)	Pakistan, 2003 to 2017, random effect model	This analysis found a substantial negative relationship between board size, CEO duality, and financial distress indicators.
4.	Elia, Toros, Sawaya, and Balouza (2021)	Lebanon, 2009 - 2018, the Z"-score model	Based on the results, the Z"-score model is recommended as an important indicator for external and internal users of banks' financial statements.
5.	Swalih, Adarsh, and Sulphey (2021)	India, 2019-2020, Two Altman Z score models,	Companies in the industry listed on the NSE are financially sound. The analysis found that the Indian automobile sector is financially stable and unlikely to face bankruptcy in the foreseeable future.
6.	Gillani et al. (2018)	Malaysia, 2018 multiple regression	It was discovered that corporate governance variables (i.e., ownership concentration, board size, board composition, CEO duality, level of board independence from management, and managerial ownership) are good predictors of financial difficulty.
7.	Shahwan (2015)	Egypt, 2008, logistic regression model	The findings demonstrate a negative correlation between CG practices and financial performance. Additionally, there is substantial positive correlation between CG practices and financial difficulties.
8.	Mariano, Izadi, and Pratt (2021)	U.K., 2010 and 2018, regression	Larger boards and greater director remuneration can minimize the likelihood of financial trouble, whereas corporate loans can enhance it. Empirical analysis of corporate borrowing is a novel contribution to the literature.

Source: Authors Construction

Theoretical Background

Jensen and Meckling (1976) described agency theory as a contract between owners and management. According to Fama and Jensen (1983), there is an inherent conflict of interest

between the agent and the principal. This can occur when shareholders and directors prioritize their interests over others. Companies have collapsed due to agency problems or corporate governance structure

complications, resulting in financial instability and stakeholder destruction (Davis, 1993; Dibra, 2016). Gillan and Martin (2007) identified failures in corporate governance and board strategy at Enron due to the conflict of interest among

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board members resulting in the manipulation of asset valuations, prices, and financial positions. Without a well-structured board, companies are vulnerable to agency difficulties, which can lead to financial wrongdoing such as money laundering, bribery, and tax evasion. According to agency theory, appointing independent directors is essential for good management (Fama & Jensen, 1983).

Hypothesis Development

The study's analysis focuses on five variables including the board of directors' size, independence, diversity, activity, and the audit committee size, and two firm-level variables (e.g. return on equity, and solvency). These are:

Board Size

Empirical research by Gales and Kesner (1994) on paired samples show that corporations that file for bankruptcy have fewer directors on their boards. The size of the board of directors, as defined by the number of board members at the organization, may be ineffectual in carrying out its supervisory tasks, resulting in decreased board performance. As a result, the business is likely to experience financial difficulties (Agustina, 2021). So, the hypothesis on the size of the board is as follows:

H₁: There is a negative relation between Board size and financial stability.

Board Independence

According to Daily and Dalton (1994), a heavily dependent board of directors can worsen a company's inflexibility, limiting its ability to change and respond to crises. Research by Elloumi and Gueyié (2001) suggests that firms with a high share of independent directors are less likely to declare bankruptcy. Fich and Slezak (2008) found that smaller boards with independent directors are more effective in addressing financial difficulties. So, the hypothesis on the size of the board is as follows:

H₂: There is a significant relationship between board independence and financial stability.

Board Diversity

Female leaders tend to be more cautious and risk-averse than male leaders (Kristanti, Rahayu, & Huda, 2016). The presence of female CEOs in a firm can impact the concept of high risk, high return. However, taking too little risk might lead to low results. Small returns might cause financial pain. Research by Kristanti et al. (2016) indicates a positive association between women in firm leadership and financial difficulty. So, the hypothesis on the size of the board is as follows:

H₃: There is a positive relation between board diversity and financial stability.

Research Methodology

Sample and Data Source

The study's data set includes 17 manufacturing companies in the Food and Allied industries that are listed on Bangladesh's Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) between 2012 and 2023. The study uses 204 firm-year observations to conduct the research. The sample size for the investigation is obtained using the Yamane (1967) formula. The DSE currently lists 21 manufacturing enterprises. Using Yamane's (1967) formula, the study's sample size is 11 Food and Allied Companies. The data were gathered from the annual reports of the tested companies.

Model and Analysis of Study

This study examined the association between company performance and financial stability using a pooled OLS regression analysis, as well as a fixed effect and random effect models. The dependent variable is each company's Altman Z Model score, whereas the independent factors are corporate governance and firm-specific variables. So, the model of the effect of corporate governance on financial stability is:

Board Activity

Brick and Chidambaran (2008) discovered a favorable relationship between board activity and business value. Adams (2003), which shows that board's respond to bad performance by increasing their degree of board participation. This may lead to an increase in board activity, since directors, for example, may desire to avoid being blamed for failing to act when necessary. In the context of the study, a large number of meetings may represent the efficiency of the firm. So, the hypothesis on the size of the board is as follows:

H₄: There is a significant relation between board activity and financial stability.

Audit Committee Size

The number of members on the audit committee determines its size. According to Miglani, Ahmed, and Henry (2015), audit committee size does not change significantly between financially challenged and non-distressed organizations. According to Pearce and Zahra (1992) resource dependence hypothesis, there is a positive correlation between the size of an audit committee and business financial success. So, the hypothesis on the size of the board is as follows:

H₅: There is a significant relationship between audit committee size and financial stability.

$$FS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 BDIVE_{it} + \beta_4 BA_{it} + \beta_5 AC_{it} + \beta_6 ROE_{it} + \beta_7 SOL_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

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Measures of Variables of the Study

Dependent Variable: The study has utilized one dependent variable to predict financial stability for this study. Financial stability is determined by Altman’s Z-Score. After almost forty years, Altman’s Z-Score (1968) is still widely regarded by researchers as an indicator of a company’s financial well-being. In 1993, Altman revised his model and felt this revised model significantly improved the predictive ability of his model and made it simpler to incorporate.

$Z = 3.25 + 6.56 X_1 + 3.26 X_2 + 6.72 X_3 + 1.05 X_4$	
<i>X</i>	Working capital divided by total assets
<i>X</i>	Retained earnings divided by total assets
<i>X</i>	Net profit before interest and tax by total assets
<i>X</i>	Book Value of Equity by total liabilities
Criteria	
A company is financially instable if its Z score ranges less than 1.1; While, companies having a Z-score between 1.1 and 2.60 is categorized in a grey area (in a crisis) company, and importantly having a Z Score > 2.60 is categorized as in the stable zone.	

Independent Variables: The construction of corporate governance variables, and firm level variables for empirical analysis is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Description of variables

Dependent Variables:		
Financial Stability	FS	determined by Altman’s Z-Score
Governance Variables:		
Board size	BS	number of directors on the board
Board independence	BI	the proportion of independent directors on the board
Board diversity	BDIVE	the proportion of female director on board
Board activity	BA	the number of board meetings held in a particular year
Audit Committee Size	AC	number of directors on the audit committee
Firm-level Variables:		
ROE	ROE	net income divided by total shareholders’ equity
Solvency	SOL	total shareholders’ equity divided by total assets

Source: Authors Construction

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors Construction

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Study

The descriptive statistics results provided in Table 2 show the mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of sample companies. The above output table shows that there are 204 observations (N), the minimum value of financial instability is -95.22, the maximum value is 48.01, the mean value is 0.86, and the standard deviation is 17.94.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
FS	204	-95.22	48.01	0.86	17.94
BS	204	4.00	11.00	6.62	0.21
BI	204	0.00	5.00	1.71	0.98
BDIVE	204	0.00	3.00	0.92	0.91
BA	204	4.00	20.00	8.50	3.46
AC	204	2.00	9.00	3.68	1.49
ROE	204	-9.37	1.35	-14.74	1.75
SOL	204	-10.31	4.14	-0.29	2.09

Source: Authors Construction

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This means that the majority of enterprises are at risk. The board size value (minimum) is 4, while the board size value (maximum) is 11, with a mean value of 6.62 and a standard deviation of 0.21. The board's independence value (minimum) is 0, and its independence value (maximum) is 5, with a mean value of 1.71 and a standard deviation of 0.21. The proportion of women on board (minimum) is 0.00, while the maximum is 3. The mean value is 0.92, with a standard deviation of 0.91. The number (minimum) is four, and the Board activity (maximum) is twenty; the mean value is 8.5, with a standard deviation of 3.46. The audit committee has a minimum size of two and a maximum of nine members; the mean value is 3.68 with a standard deviation of 1.49. The average ROE and Solvency are -14.74 and -0.29, respectively, ranging from (-10.31 to 1.35) and (-10.31 to 4.14), with 1.75 and 2.09 standard deviations.

Pearson's Correlation

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	FS	BS	BI	BDIVE	BA	AC	ROE	SOL
FS	1.000							
BS	-0.150**	1.000						
BI	-0.009	0.144**	1.000					
BDIVE	-0.002	-0.115*	0.022	1.000				
BA	0.287***	0.206***	0.068	0.205***	1.000			
AC	-0.160**	0.581***	0.157**	-0.168***	0.211***	1.000		
ROE	0.041	-0.171***	-0.141**	-0.012	0.187***	0.066	1.000	
SOL	0.751***	-0.044	-0.044	-0.004	0.267***	-0.198***	-0.011	1.000

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Source: Authors Construction

A correlation coefficient is a statistical tool that shows how two or more variables tend to fluctuate together. In Table 3, the correlation coefficient between FS and BS is -0.150. The correlation coefficients for FS, BI, BDIVE, BA, AC, ROE, and SOL are as follows -0.009, -0.002, 0.287, -0.160, 0.041, and 0.751. Table 3 shows no evidence of multi-collinearity. FS is significantly correlated with BS, BA, AC, and SOL.

Multivariate Analysis

Table 4: POLS Regression Outcomes

	Regression Co-efficient		
	FS	FEM	REM
BS	-3.442*** (.42)	-2.25*** (.539)	-2.46*** (.493)
BI	1.242** (.6)	.212** (.583)	.358 (.56)
BDIVE	.288 (.662)	.299 (1.319)	.208 (1.112)
BA	.379** (.192)	.463* (.253)	.493** (.233)
AC	2.618*** (.506)	2.091*** (.482)	2.162*** (.462)
ROE	-.002 (.006)	-.011** (.005)	-.01** (.005)
SOL	7.865*** (.166)	7.345*** (.168)	7.418*** (.159)
Constant	11.25*** (2.601)	5.453 (3.509)	6.207* (3.724)
Number of obs	204	204	204
F-test	389.530	425.667	
Prob > F	0.000	0.000	0.000
R-squared	0.933	0.943	0.928
Hausman (1978) specification test			
Chi-square test value	22.83		
P-value	0.000		

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

Source: Authors Construction

Table 4 shows the multivariate result of the model. The results demonstrate the first hypothesis proposes that board size has an opposite impact on financial stability. This hypothesis implies that a large number of board sizes effect adversely on financial stability. The study found that board size had a negative coefficient with a 1% significance level. Thus, the first hypothesis is empirically supported, and these findings are aligned with (Manzaneque, Priego, & Merino, 2016). Next, the hypothesis proposes that board independence has a positive impact on financial stability. This hypothesis implies that the more independent members in the board the less

possibility of financial stability. The study found that board independence has a positive coefficient with a 5% significance level. Thus, the second hypothesis is empirically supported, and these findings is aligned with Pandapotan and Puspitasari (2022). The study found that board diversity has a positive coefficient. Thus, the third hypothesis is empirically supported, which is aligned with (Kalbuana, Taqi, Uzliawati, & Ramdhani, 2022). The fourth hypothesis testing finds that the more board activity of the company the more the company is financially secure with a 5% significance level. Thus, the fourth hypothesis is empirically supported, this

finding is aligned with (Dissanayke, Somathilake, Madushanka, Wickramasinghe, & Cooray, 2017). The study found that audit committee size has a positive coefficient with 1% significance, which is the last hypothesis. Thus, the last hypothesis is empirically supported, which is aligned with Siswanto and Fuad (2017). The table also displays fixed and random effect results. The Hausman test found that fixed effect model is more appropriate for the model.

Conclusion

This research emphasizes the impact of corporate governance, specifically board

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composition, in alleviating financial stability in emerging economies. The findings show that boards with a higher share of independent directors and gender diversity are better able to control managerial decision-making, increase transparency, and minimize the chance of financial crisis. Furthermore, the members of audit committee promote better risk management and financial stability. These findings highlight the necessity of enhancing corporate governance frameworks in emerging markets to promote long-term growth and resilience to economic difficulties.

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Nurturing Bangladesh Remittance Inflow More Keenly

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Bangladesh is an over populated country with huge labor surplus. And a significant portion of population are working as migrant all over the world and putting contribution to build better Bangladesh by sending hard work remittance. Remittances is now an important part of household livelihood strategies.

A remittance is a non-commercial transfer of money by a foreign worker, a member of a diaspora community, or a citizen with familial ties abroad, for household income in their home country or homeland. Money sent home by migrants competes with international aid as one of the largest financial inflows to developing countries. Workers' remittances are a significant part of international capital flows, especially with regard to labor-exporting countries. Remittance has been defined by the World Bank as the part of the earnings which a migrant worker sends back to family members in the country of origin.

Export earnings and remittance are the two main source of Bangladesh foreign currency. The number of Bangladeshi young foreign job seekers are increasing day by day. According to Bangladesh Labor Force Survey 2022, the number

of unemployed populations was about 2,582,000 out of which the number of unemployed youths aged 15-29 was 2,184,000. In addition, a good number of graduate and post graduates are added to these unemployed people every year. As per Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training (BMET), in 1976 total overseas employment who left Bangladesh was 6,087 and foreign remittance inflow in Bangladesh was USD 23.71 million. Gradually number of overseas employment had increased bringing in increased foreign currency remittance amount and in 2023 overseas employment seekers who left Bangladesh was the highest ever total at 1,305,453 number, and in 2021 highest remittance entered was USD 22070.87 million. Meanwhile, judging the early trends of FY 2024-25 the remittances may reach at USD 30 Billions in Bangladesh.

In Bangladesh, export is the main source of foreign currency and remittance is 2nd main source of foreign currency earnings which is 48% in average of gross total export earnings. But significant attention is not given on remittance like the attention given for exports. Last 5 years total export vs. remittance statistics with percentage is shown blow:

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SL No.	Financial Year	Total Export Earnings (USD in billion)	Remittance (USD in billion)	Remittance % of Export
1	2023- 2024	48.27*	23.91	50%
2	2022-2023	55.55	21.61	39%
3	2021-2022	52.08	21.03	40%
4	2020-2021	38.75	24.77	64%
5	2019-2020	33.67	18.20	54%
	Average	228.32	109.52	48%

*July-23 to May-24 (BB Monthly Economic Trend, August 2024)

Remittances in early of FY 2024-2025 is in increasing trend which indicates it may record the highest remittance in the Bangladesh history. And in previous three consecutive financial years remittance was in growing trend despite the effect of Covid-19 pandemic, effect of Russia-Ukraine war and geo political volatility. Bangladesh was the 8th highest recipient of remittances in the world with almost USD 21.50 billion in 2022 while neighboring India was 1st recipient remittances with USD 111.22 billion and Pakistan was the 5th highest recipient with USD 30.17billion according to World Bank.

As per Annual Report (July 2022-June 2023) of Bangladesh Bank, Remittance earnings of Bangladesh increased by 2.75 percent to USD 21.610 billion in FY23 from USD 21.031 billion in FY22. The report showed that country's remittance earnings increased in FY23 because of strong labor market conditions, wage hikes in the high-income destination countries, and high demand for less-skilled migrants

due to higher energy prices in the GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) countries. Apparently, Russia-Ukraine war ignited the soaring global inflation that did not dampen the remittance flows significantly. Besides, numerous supportive policy measures like increasing cash incentives from 2.0 percent to 2.5 percent for the remitters to curb the informal channels, withdrawing the interest ceiling on non-resident foreign currency deposits, imposing ceiling on internet banking transfers and removing the proof of source of income requirements along with the time and cost-effective money transfer process encourage the expatriates to remit more remittances using formal channel throughout the fiscal year in the Gulf and the Middle East region, especially in countries of Oman, Kuwait, the UAE, Qatar, Bahrain and Saudi Arabia.

Chief Adviser of Bangladesh's interim government Nobel Laureate Prof Muhammad Yunus addressed the 79th

session of the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) on 27th September 2024. In that speech he mentioned about 15 million Bangladeshi diaspora live and work worldwide. In order for migration to be beneficial for all, we have to create pathways for safe, orderly, regular, and responsible migration and mobility of people. The international community has to ensure full respect for human rights and the humane treatment of migrants, regardless of their migration status. Going with the global phenomena on Migration, Bangladesh government is also committed to curb unsafe migration.

Overseas employment has also been increased over the decades. As per Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training (BMET) data year by year (since 1976-2023) outgoing number of overseas employment and respective year remittance inflows shown as under:

Year	Total Employment	Total Remittance in million USD
1976	6,087	23.71
1977	15,725	82.79
1978	22,809	106.9
1979	24,495	172.06
1980	30,073	301.33
1981	55,787	304.88
1982	62,762	490.77
1983	59,220	627.51
1984	56,714	500
1985	77,694	500
1986	68,658	576.2
1987	74,017	747.6
1988	68,121	763.9
1989	101,724	757.84
1990	103,814	781.54
1991	147,156	769.3
1992	188,124	901.97
1993	244,508	1009.09
1994	186,326	1153.54
1995	187,543	1201.52
1996	211,714	1355.34
1997	231,077	1525.03
1998	267,667	1599.24
1999	168,182	1806.63
2000	222,686	1954.54
2001	189,060	2071.03
2002	225,256	2847.79
2003	254,190	3177.63
2004	272,958	3565.31
2005	252,702	4249.87
2006	381,516	5484.08
2007	832,609	6562.71
2008	875,055	8979.00
2009	475,278	10717.73
2010	390,702	11004.73
2011	568,062	12168.09
2012	607,798	14163.93
2013	409,253	13832.13
2014	425,684	14942.57
2015	555,881	15270.99
2016	757,731	13609.77
2017	1,008,525	13526.84
2018	734,181	15544.68
2019	700,159	18354.94
2020	217,669	21752.27
2021	617,209	22070.87
2022	1,135,873	21285.21
2023	1,305,453	21942.76
Total	16,075,487.	297,138.16

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Remittance earnings represent almost 50% in average of last five years total export. So all sorts of sector barriers need to be identified properly and addressed in time to continue the growth of remittance and employment abroad with safe pathway and law costs.

As per Monetary Policy Review 2023-2024 of Bangladesh Bank "Remittance inflows registered at USD 19.1 billion, growing by 7.9 percent during July-April of FY24, while the growth rate was 2.75 percent in FY23 (Chart

III.13). The highest amount of remittance was received mainly from the Gulf region, which accounts for about half (48.8 percent) of the total remittances. During July-April, FY24, remittances from Saudi Arabia decreased by 28.8 percent. The UAE, the Euro region, Malaysia, and the UK contributed significantly to maintain the improved growth in country's remittance inflows. On the other hand, remittance from the USA declined by 25.3 percent during the same period of FY24 (Chart III.14). However,

to enhance the workers' remittances with the high growth of overseas employment, the government and the BB have taken few need based multifaceted policies like dual incentive scheme, the double limit for remittances to individual mobile financial service (MFS) account, expanded remittance channels, streamlined banking regulations, fair pricing for remittances, the 'PROBASH' pension scheme for expatriate Bangladeshis etc."

Chart III.13: Remittance Inflow and Overseas Employment (growth in percent)

Source: Bangladesh Bank and Bureau of Manpower, Employment, and Training
* July – April, FY24

Chart III.14: Region/Country-wise Growth of Remittance Inflows (in percent)

Source: Bangladesh Bank.
* July – April, FY24.

Overseas employment has been playing a vital role to the national economy of Bangladesh as well as its continuous development. Bangladeshi migrant workers abroad are imparting in them substantial financial power in Bangladesh. For example, recent upheavals were vividly supported by a group of migrant workers who declared remittance shut down. This had resulted into significant fall of remittance amount in July 2024 USD 1.913.77 billion from USD 2.538 billion in June 2024.

who were power oligarchs having influence in Govt. & were earlier not brought into lawful actions Malpractice and irregularities by a "syndicate" of Bangladeshi recruiting agencies need to be identified and

addressed strictly to ensure low-cost but highly skilled labor export for a higher remittance inflow. In some cases, Bangladeshi migrant workers have been & are being forced to face brutality & greed of recruiting agent syndicates frequently. For example, it is reported few years back that a former Bangladeshi MP was punished in Kuwait for human trafficking, facilitating migrant worker travel on fake contracts. A Kuwait court sentenced him to four-year imprisonment, after around seven months of trial in a case filed for bribery and human trafficking and an Appeal Court has sentenced him for another three years of imprisonment (in total 7 years). At the same time, he had been fined by around BDT 56.32 crore (KWD20 lakh). Present Govt. has plan to file

cases against the syndicate & exporters of manpower

Malaysia is one of the top migration destination countries at low costs for the Bangladeshi manpower exports and high remittance earnings. Malaysia froze its recruitment from Bangladesh in 2018 as well as this year because of the anomalies. Recently, the Daily Star reported that 16,970 people have failed to reach Malaysia for mismanagement. The Daily Star also reported on 31 May 2024 "Recruitment in Malaysia: Syndicate siphons over \$1b out of Bangladesh". The report also shown how the recruiting agencies extracted BDT 542,000 from each worker instead of Tk. 78,990 set for going to Malaysia.

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MONEY TAKEN FROM EACH WORKER GOING TO MALAYSIA (ESTIMATE)	
Local and Malaysian syndicate	Tk 107,000
Fees workers not supposed to pay	Tk 190,000
Recruitment agent	Tk70,000
BMET	Tk 5,000
Medical test, registration	Tk 10,000
Plane ticket	Tk 100,000
Local brokers	Tk 60,000
Total	Tk 542,000

On December 19, 2021, Bangladesh and Malaysia signed a memorandum of understanding, according to which, a workers would need to spend no more than Tk 78,990 for the passport, health checkup, registration, welfare, insurance, identity card, clothing, and recruitment agency fees.

In early October 2024 the Chief Adviser Prof Muhammad Yunus exchanged greetings with Malaysian Prime Minister Anwar Ibrahim on a short visit at Dhaka and held bilateral talks. They discussed the possibility of signing new agreements on agriculture, energy, education, the semiconductor industry, the blue economy, innovation, defense, and youth development. The meeting discussed how Malaysia can take more workers and

professionals from Bangladesh through multiple entry visas. Mr. Ibrahim said that he would consider the entry of 18,000 Bangladeshis to his country as soon as possible, if all conditions are met in respect of those Bangladeshi migrant workers who could not reach Malaysia by the May 31 deadline mainly because of shortage of flights.

As remittance by the overseas employees is the second largest source of foreign currency earnings in Bangladesh which is also in growing trend. To boost the remittance inflow and continuing the upward trend, a number measures need to be taken by the government and its related agencies both in short and long term basis. This may include:

Skilled and professional migrant workers can earn much more foreign currency comparing to the unskilled but a lion's share of Bangladeshi migrant workers in abroad are unskilled. Government and its agencies related to the foreign employment should find out the requirements of foreign recruiting countries and its relevant agencies. Effective measures should be taken to meet the requirements and necessary awareness program should be taken and published about the rule of destination country before an expatriate leave Bangladesh.

Manpower development is one of the key sources of productivity and output so

according to the requirement of manpower importers, sufficient skills need to be developed for the job seekers with easy access as well low costs. Attention in quality education system especially technical, vocational education systems, technical training centers and information technology (IT) training centers may play a vital role to develop more skilled and smart workers.

Language is very important for the communication in the destination country of an expatriate. As for example job seekers in South Korea, Japan etc., a certain level language skill of the respective country is a pre-requisite. Language teaching center facility need to be available and affordable for the youth job seekers. Government of Bangladesh can undertake various short-term, medium-term and long-term schemes to financially help employment seekers to establish career and earn livelihood for the potential expatriate who have permanently returned to Bangladesh.

Prevent money laundering which may include campaigning to create awareness to the expatriates, money exchange facility increasing like agent banking in remote areas where no bank or branch exists so that the ultimate receiver can get the available and easy facility to withdraw the remittance. Exchange house increasing at abroad by the Bangladeshi Banks to reduce dependency on

money laundering (Hundi). Expatriate normally follow two methods “formal banking channel and “Hundi” to repatriate remittance in Bangladesh though Hundi is informal routes. A group of workers particularly the unskilled like “Hundi” option resulting Bangladesh to be deprived from much needed foreign currency inflow in official channel on record.

All sorts of malpractices and irregularities must be addressed and Bangladesh government must show zero tolerance and act to dismantle the syndicates. The Anti-Corruption Commission must investigate any allegations of corruption, raise cases on money laundering by the manpower

agents to demonstrate exemplary punishment of malpractice and irregularities.

Workers usually aspire respect and quick support from Bangladesh embassies/foreign office. So, Embassy/foreign office staffs should be trained to approach and extend extra-ordinary level need based support to the expatriate.

Foreign employment related organization like BOESL should search effectively new labor market and requirements review for Bangladeshi youth job seekers abroad and signing more MoU for manpower recruitment at low & affordable migration costs and in an ethical way.

Since long, there are lot of allegations about airport harassment faced by the workers at airports while they travelled to Bangladesh. To continue the upward trend remittance and contribution to increase foreign currency reserve, all sorts of harassment at airport in Bangladesh should be identified and addressed timely giving remitters motivations, complacency & pride from being remitters.

To conclude as remittances is the 2nd main source of foreign currency in Bangladesh and remittance is now an important part of household livelihood strategies across the country particularly in huge number of rural families. And Bangladesh has a long-time experience and

Top Countries Receiving Money From Abroad	2000	Top Countries Receiving Money From Abroad	2023e
India	\$13B	India	\$125B
France	\$9B	Mexico	\$67B
Mexico	\$8B	China	\$50B
Philippines	\$7B	Philippines	\$40B
UK	\$5B	France	\$34B
Türkiye	\$5B	Pakistan	\$24B
South Korea	\$5B	Egypt	\$24B
U.S.	\$4B	Bangladesh	\$23B
Portugal	\$4B	Nigeria	\$21B
Germany	\$4B	Guatemala	\$20B

Note: 2023 figures are estimates. All numbers rounded.

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advancement in exporting manpower of skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled level. The Indian diaspora measuring nearly 18 million people collectively sent more than \$125 billion back to the country in 2023. In fact, India became the first country to ever receive more than \$100 billion in personal remittances in 2022. Comparing Indian migrant workers, Bangladeshi migrant workers are poor in skilled and technical ground. Top 10 Countries Remittances Received (2000-2023):

Bangladesh is in 8th position in the list, marking a significant progress. Yet hurdles, bureaucratic procrastinations & volatile government policies need corrections. Bangladesh Government should identify to effectively bring in more FCY inflows from this sector. Bangladesh Government should plan to optimize its labor surplus employment scopes abroad for increased remittance earnings & accelerating economic development with sustainability.

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Role of Invoice Discounting to Bridge the Estimated MSME Finance Gap in South Asian Countries

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Abstract

Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) are not just entities, but a powerful force behind employment, innovation, and economic growth. Their potential to drive economic development and combat poverty in emerging economies is immense. Access to financing, often a significant barrier, can be overcome with a greater understanding of the financial divide. This understanding will enable the public and private sectors to address this issue more effectively. By measuring the MSME finance gap, governors, bankers, and other private sector participants can focus on high-potential growth areas and thereby more effectively promote MSME sector development. This study aims to compare South Asian countries, highlight the significance of digital technology like invoice discounting, and clarify how it bridges the estimated finance gap.

Introduction

MSMEs, which employ 90% of the labor force and provide between (40 and 60) % of the GDP of most nations, are widely acknowledged as the foundation and backbone of all economies worldwide. With over 90% of all businesses and over 50% of all jobs worldwide, micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are the foundation of global economies. In addition to promoting

entrepreneurship and innovation, they are essential for diversifying economies, building competitiveness, and building resilience in the face of financial difficulties.

In South Asia, MSMEs, a diverse and complex network, are prevalent across the economy and engage in agriculture, services, and manufacturing. For instance, a staggering 99 % of all non-farm enterprises in Bangladesh fall into the MSME category, employing 20.3 million Bangladeshi workers. The distribution of enterprises by broad economic activities and size reveals that most MSMEs operate non-manufacturing activities (around 90%). However, 50 % of medium-sized businesses undertake manufacturing activities, adding to the variety and complexity of these enterprises.

MSMEs, with their significant role in the economies of South Asian countries, hold immense potential for future growth. In Sri Lanka, they account for 45 % of the country's employment and 52 % of the GDP. In Pakistan, they are responsible for 78 % of the industrial employment and 40 % of the GDP. In Nepal, approximately 10 % of MSEs are involved in manufacturing, which rises to 20 % for medium-sized enterprises. The Maldives, due to its size, has a different MSME profile. Outside the capital, where tourism is a significant sector, the MSMEs in more remote areas are heavily involved in fisheries and agriculture, hinting at their

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future contribution to the economy.

According to estimates from the International Finance Corporation (IFC), the unmet funding needs of 65 million firms, or 40% of formal micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in developing countries, amount to \$5.2 trillion annually. This amount is equivalent to 1.4 times the present global MSME lending level. In emerging economies, formal MSMEs account for up to 40% of GDP. When informal MSMEs are considered, these figures rise dramatically. Creating opportunities for MSMEs in emerging markets is crucial to advancing economic development and reducing poverty. The private and public sectors can better address this matter if they have better insights into the magnitude and nature of the financial gap. Hence, sizing the MSME finance

gap is crucial for the governors, financiers, and other private sector players to target high-potential growth areas and, hence, more efficiently support MSME sector development.

The World Bank (2019) projects that 600 million jobs will be required by 2030 to accommodate the expanding global workforce, which is why many governments worldwide have prioritized MSME growth. MSMEs account for seven out of ten formal jobs created in emerging markets. Access to financing, however, is a significant barrier to MSME expansion and the second most common issue MSMEs face when trying to expand in developing and emerging markets.

In Bangladesh, MSMEs employ 30% of the workforce and contribute 25% to the GDP.

However, due to their informal nature, they need help accessing government support and obtaining loans from financial institutions (Siddique, 2022). Banks are hesitant to lend to MSMEs due to their inability to provide collateral, and loan recovery is unpredictable. MSMEs using accounts receivable finance may benefit from increased liquidity and financial stability.

The Government of India has set an ambitious goal of doubling the Indian economy to US\$ 5 trillion in five years. To achieve this, it has created career opportunities for the young population and recognized the potential of MSMEs as crucial employment generators. The government's promotion of MSMEs to create new jobs in the sector indicates the potential these enterprises hold. Furthermore, the government aims to enhance MSME's export share and contribution to GDP.

In Pakistan, an estimated demand for SME financing is Rs. (3-4) trillion. Only 15-20% of this demand is met by formal funding, while the rest is fulfilled through informal channels such as family and friends. A significant portion of the market still needs to be met. Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are expected to benefit from the growth of the Islamic finance industry. As of June 2022, the share of Islamic finance has increased year over year from 24% to 27%, and the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) aims to raise this share further

to 35%. Islamic finance may provide crucial support to businesses. In 2021, the Pakistani government launched the "Kamyab Jawan" program to boost the SME sector in the country (Khan et al., 2021).

- To bridge the finance gap, traditional financing options can be cumbersome, time-consuming, and sometimes inaccessible to smaller businesses. However, invoice discounting has emerged as a viable and efficient solution for MSMEs to raise

funds quickly. Technology integration into invoice discounting has revolutionized this process, making it more accessible, transparent, and efficient.

The advancement of technology has turned invoice discounting into a powerful and effective fundraising tool for MSMEs. MSMEs can overcome traditional financing barriers through automation, data analytics, blockchain, and digital platforms and enhance their cash flow management. As technology progresses, the

invoice discounting will become even more efficient and secure. This will address the challenges MSMEs face when seeking credit facilities and the limited support financial institutions provide to improve credit flow to the MSME sector (Express Computer, 2024).

Supply chain financing (SCF) can benefit corporations, their suppliers, and factors in the supply chain ecosystem. The funding and liquidity that MSMEs need to meet their ongoing working capital requirements are not readily

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available. SCF allows MSMEs to obtain loans at a reduced cost and with less paperwork. Invoice discounting, overdraft facilities, and factoring are the three most popular kinds of digital technology that can foster the MSME sector and bridge the estimated finance gap.

Methodology

The study used data from various secondary sources, including official publications and research papers. In particular, the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises of Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan's annual report, the South Asian MSME Finance Gap Report released over several years, served as a secondary data source.

MSMEs in Bangladesh

Bangladesh's SME Policy 2019 governs the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector. According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB), 99% of formal enterprises/businesses in Bangladesh are MSMEs. These MSMEs, with their significant role in employment generation, provide livelihoods to a large portion of the population, generating 75% of non-agricultural employment. Manufacturing MSMEs contribute 25% to the GDP. MSMEs comprise a large percentage of the industrial landscape in Bangladesh. The Planning Division of Bangladesh states that MSMEs account for 45% of manufacturing value

added, 90% of industrial units, and 80% of industrial employment, including cottage enterprises. Approximately 6% of MSMEs increase each year (Hossain, 2021). In Bangladesh, MSMEs account for a meager 25% of GDP, while in Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam, 59%, 58%, Cambodia, and 40% of GDP, respectively. This is despite their relevance. SME Policy (2019) states that the nation hopes to raise the GDP contribution of MSMEs from 25% to 32% by 2024. To facilitate and encourage MSME exports, businesses exporting 80% or more of their products are eligible for duty-free import of machinery and spares. The bank also introduced an Islamic finance fund to enhance the role of Islamic banks. Due to the effective policies of the Bangladesh Bank, 25% of the consolidated loan book of commercial banks is dedicated to SMEs.

MSMEs in India

Based on Kumar et al. (2017), the MSME sector has become a dynamic market essential to maintaining the economic equilibrium of the nation. Its micro, small, and medium enterprises are the backbone and driving force behind the nation's economic expansion (Chendaiah & Vani, 2014). Some prominent features of India's MSME sector are the MSME policy directive of a 40% bank credit earmarked for priority sector lending, specialized SME bank branches for easy access to credit in industrial clusters (2014 specialized MSME

branches),²⁵ the Udyam registration portal replaced former filing process for registration of MSMEs.

Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) constitute the backbone of the Indian economy, with a predicted growth from 6.3 crore to 7.5 crore shortly (IBEF, 2024). There is still a long way to go for MSMEs in India. The country's MSME sector has been finding it difficult to persevere and stay competitive in various sectors amid economic uncertainty.

As of March 2024, data from the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises indicates

that the number of MSMEs registered on the Udyam site, which includes the Udyam Assist Platform (UAP), has reached 4,00,42,875, with a continual increase recorded (Soni, 2024). 3,93,18,355, or around 97.7% of them, are classified as micro-enterprises. Small enterprises comprise 6,08,935, or around 1.5%, of all registered enterprises, while medium-sized enterprises comprise 55,488, or roughly 0.8%. According to an EY analysis, only about 14% of India's 64 million MSMEs have access to formal credit, and the country's MSME sector has a \$530 billion credit gap (MSME Desk, 2024).

MSME in Pakistan

According to the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP), the percentage of MSMEs getting formal credit is only 8.5%, with 181,000 borrowers at the end of 2018 (Khan et al., 2021). MSMEs are vital to Pakistan's economy. They generate a third of Pakistan's GDP, providing inclusive growth, new jobs, and skill development. Pakistan spends a mere 1% of its GDP on MSME financing, which is far less compared to regional countries India (9%), Bangladesh (10%), and Sri Lanka (8%). That results in Pakistan's MSMEs being unable to thrive.

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With over 5.2 million MSMEs in Pakistan, the sector represents almost 90 % of businesses, contributing approximately 40 % to the GDP and 30 % to the total exports. The SME market also provides employment opportunities to 80% of the country's non-agriculture labor force. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA) is an autonomous institution of the Government of Pakistan under the Ministry of Industries and Production. SMEDA is not only an SME policy-advisory body for the government of Pakistan but also facilitates other stakeholders in addressing their SME development agendas. Of the 5 million total businesses in Pakistan, 4.5 million are estimated to be MSMEs, which contribute 40% to the country's GDP and 80% of employment to non-farm labor.

MSME Finance Gap

The MSME finance gap assumes that the firms in a developing

country have the same willingness and ability to borrow as their counterparts in well-developed credit markets and operate in comparable institutional environments — and that financial institutions lend at similar intensities as their benchmarked counterparts. In recognition of the need to quantify the extent of the MSME finance gap, the International Finance Corporation (IFC) partnered with McKinsey & Company in 2010 to estimate the gap (Stain et al., 2010). The difference between the current supply and potential demand—which financial institutions may be able to address—is known as the MSME finance gap.

In South Asia, the MSME finance gap of Afghanistan as % of GDP is 24.43%, followed by Sri Lanka (20.80%), Bangladesh (19.98%), Nepal (17.25%), Pakistan (15.20%), India (11.10%) and Bhutan (4.66%).

Why this Finance Gap?

Getting bank and other financial institution financing is difficult for MSMEs since they usually need to maintain sufficient records to handle their tax reports, business papers, transactions, etc. A growing number of MSMEs are new businesses founded by individuals who have never used credit as first-time borrowers. Several factors frequently contribute to the lack of growth capital for MSMEs deemed higher risk, including • lack of physical collateral. • inadequate risk/reward balance. • frequently unreliable financials. • expensive cost to serve. • higher regulatory capital necessary for unsecured lending, etc.

Bridging the Gap by Forming a Digital Technology

In today's dynamic micro, small, and medium-sized enterprise (MSME) landscape, maintaining a healthy cash flow is crucial for meeting compliance and sustaining business growth. Traditional funding is no longer sufficient to meet the demands and goals of these companies. Therefore, technology-driven modern finance is well-placed to bridge the growing working capital gap caused by the limitations of traditional banking institutions.

Cutting-edge technology powers contemporary solutions like invoice discounting, enabling them to provide unparalleled user interfaces,

Figure 1: MSME Finance Gap (South Asia)

Source: Hossen and Uddin (2024)

improved usability, and—most importantly—dynamic pricing and usage. In theory, invoice discounting is the most excellent supplier finance option accessible. The invoice discounting currently in use is significantly better than any earlier discounting strategies that may have been employed in the past, despite the argument made by some that it has existed for as long as MSMEs have had cash flow problems.

Blockchain, or distributed ledger technology, is one of the technologies with numerous uses in this area. Blockchain, a decentralized cryptocurrency database, ensures that a transaction, once recorded, cannot be altered, or tampered with. Invoice discounting platforms like Xpedize leverage machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms to analyze large

volumes of data, thereby assessing fraud and credit risk. These technologies also enable the creation of algorithm-based auctions that accurately determine the best terms of payment and discount percentages.

What Is Invoice Discounting?

Invoice financing, an innovative approach to supply chain finance, offers a convenient way to manage supplier payments. By partnering with an Invoice Finance Provider, your company can obtain funding quickly after invoicing, whether a single invoice or a batch. This convenience allows for efficiently deploying resources for business expansion or cash flow without additional security. Conventional business payment terms are typically 30, 60, 90, or 120 days, as agreed upon.

Small enterprises manage their cash while borrowing from friends and relatives. After achieving some milestones to sustain continued growth, they opt for invoice discounting, a form of short-term borrowing against unpaid invoices, to manage the liquidity to develop their business. Essentially, in invoice discounting, a business sells its accounts receivable (invoices) to a third-party financier (usually a bank or a specialized invoice discounting Non-Banking Financial Company) at a discount. The client will be given a certain amount of time to pay the firm after issuing the invoice. If a master invoice discounting facility—which manages the process—is active, the company may discount invoices with specific clients up to the predetermined maximum value levels (Figure 2).

Figure 2: How does invoice discounting work?

Source: Trade Finance Global, 2024

Role of Invoice Discounting to Bridge the Estimated MSME Finance Gap in South Asian Countries

Bangladesh and Invoice Discounting

Supply chain finance (SCF), a financial innovation introduced in Bangladesh by IDLC Finance Limited in 1999, offers significant advantages to buyers. It provides them with a secured loan, enhancing their balance sheet performance, meeting their working capital needs, and creating new business opportunities.

Factoring and bill discounting are two examples of these financial instruments. Both financial instruments support businesses based on raised invoices, primarily micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). Both products are short-term trade financing alternatives that depend on future receivables through sales or transfers of the rights before the due date. In Bangladesh, factoring is the most popular form of supplier financing. In Bangladesh, there are enormous opportunities for supply chain

finance, and the regulatory bodies are encouraging investment in the MSME sector.

The advance sale of a bill to an intermediary before its due date is known as bill discounting. A third party is involved in factoring and is positioned between the supplier and the buyer. The factor, or third party, pays a discounted price for an organization's outstanding invoices. How the services are provided distinguishes factoring from bill discounting. While the bill discounting facility places great importance on the drawer's banker creditworthiness, factors in factoring provide services depending on the debtor's quality, record, and creditworthiness. "Confidential invoice discounting" is a common term for bill discounting. The idea behind factoring and bill discounting is to guarantee funding without needing extra security. The central bank is anticipated to finish crafting the regulations

for international factoring shortly. (Siddique, 2019).

India and Invoice Discounting

Out of the 64 Mn MSMEs (in India), 7.7 million, or 12%, are considered digitally mature (Choksi, 2024). Despite the presence of MSMEs in India, limited digitization and strained access to capital are two pressing issues that must be addressed systematically to set the sector on its path to development. The potential for digitization to increase significantly over the next five years, from the current level of 12%, underscores the need for immediate action. New-age finance, powered by technology, is poised to fill the growing working capital deficit left by the limitations of traditional financial institutions (Mohan, 2023).

Pakistan and Invoice Discounting

Like most developing countries, Pakistan has a "missing middle" regarding MSME financing. That means microenterprises are financed through microfinance institutions, and large corporations are financed through banks, but MSMEs remain neglected and cash-poor. Invoice Financing is a short-term financing method a business can use to get against its receivable invoices (Accounts Receivable). The primary purpose of invoice financing is to improve the business' cash flows by utilizing

the current amount yet to be received. CashNow is more than a tech product - it is the mission to empower MSMEs. The CashNow platform is Pakistan's first collateral-free invoice financing solution. Besides, like in other Muslim countries, in Pakistan, many people are reluctant to obtain financing facilities due to the involvement of interest that is forbidden according to Islamic Shariah. That is why many people seek Shariah-compliant financing solutions only.

InvoiceMate by MateSol is the world's first complete invoice management system on blockchain. The entire invoice journey from procurement to payment is transparently recorded on the blockchain, creating an immutable record verifiable by all relevant parties. Banks and other financial institutions can easily verify

invoice authenticity and relevant records to extend invoice financing facilities to businesses. This allows businesses to overcome cash flow challenges and reach their full potential. InvoiceMate facilitates Islamic principles-based invoice financing (www.invoicemate.net).

How does Invoice Discounting Solve the MSME's Finance problem?

The following is how the invoice discounting tackles the central issue of MSMEs' access to credit:

- The notion of invoice discounting aids in retaining some of the main issues of supply chain problems across the country, thereby promoting MSMEs in terms of productivity in the product's manufacturing process on a small scale.

Invoice discounting is one economic component that appears to be employed to establish the behavioral approach of the scorecard in terms of predictive analysis. This is also utilized during uncertain times, such as floods, wars, etc.

- For small and medium-sized businesses that desperately need capital to expand, the functionality of invoice discounting is a crucial aspect to develop. Recognizing the appropriate economic factors during the query service design phase is necessary to address the businesses that were not default applicants. (1) Provide an option for "trust" and anti-trust levels on the IT platform. (2) Pay attention to the groups with greater and intermediate

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Conclusion

While Micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) have struggled to secure adequate financing from traditional banks and mainstream lenders, technological advancements have opened new avenues for democratizing access to financing and various business operations. Modern technologies enable conventional financial institutions and new FinTechs to automate lending and develop new products tailored to address MSMEs' economic challenges. A significant trend in MSME financing is the global acceptance of blockchain technology-based digital supply chain financing, which is becoming increasingly commonplace. However, South Asian countries are still lagging in accessing digitization in MSME financing.

To improve MSME access to financing, policymakers must keep developing their capabilities. Despite its enormous potential, Bangladesh has a somewhat limited supply chain finance market. The insufficient understanding of supply chain finance products extends beyond the expertise of suppliers and anchors.

In India, both federal and state governments have joined forces to support MSMEs by integrating TReDS platforms. This tactic encourages private actors and stimulates digital supply chain finance platforms, providing a strong infrastructure

asset levels; (3) Encourage MSMEs to use a platform where all required information is automatically filled out quarterly to maintain the small and medium-sized businesses' positive performance. (4) Creation of the MSMEs' platform for privacy authentication seekers. This design technique is an early result of the invoice discounting method.

Flexible Solution

Dynamic Discounting

Our system is designed with efficiency in mind, benefiting both suppliers and buyers. Suppliers can choose to accept early payment in exchange for a small discount, while buyers can pay their suppliers a discounted price for every purchase. This dynamic system, which we call 'flexible payment terms', allows

suppliers to manage their working capital according to their business needs. In other words, the more days early the payment, the larger the discount, creating a direct correlation between the discount and the days paid in advance.

TReDS (Trade Receivables Electronic Discounting System)

A significant benefit of Xpedize's integration with TReDS exchanges is the ability for Buyer businesses to select TReDS as a competitive source of financing for the early payment request made by their Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) Suppliers. TReDS is an online marketplace where MSMEs can use several lenders to lower their trade receivables.

that combines technology and legal requirements to help include MSMEs in the financial system.

It is crucial to have a collaborative effort involving the government, financial institutions, educational institutions, and industry stakeholders to create a supportive ecosystem for the sustained growth of MSMEs in South Asian countries.

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Recognition of ICAB membership by ICAEW

Membership Scheme of The Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales (ICAEW) allows the members of ICAB to apply for ICAEW membership based on their experiences.

Eligibility criteria of this membership scheme are a series of questions which assess ICAB Member's experience, achievements, skills and expertise. Each application must be supported by an eligible sponsor. Applicants need to complete an Examination of Experience.

Details of ICAEW Membership Scheme is available at <http://www.icaew.com/membership/becoming-a-member/members-of-other-bodies/campaigns/pathways-to-membership>.

ICAB signed its first Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW) in 2009. Since then, ICAB has been working with ICAEW as the learning and professional development partner, and also recognized as an approved tuition provider of ICAEW.

As per MoU, ICAB Members can be the members of ICAEW after successful completion of 04 papers out of 15. These members have the opportunity to apply for UK Practising Certificate (PC) subject to meeting the standard ICAEW PC requirement.

Recognition of ICAB Membership by CIPFA, UK

Members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) are eligible to apply for membership of the Chartered Institute of Public Finance and Accountancy (CIPFA), a globally recognised membership body for the public sector.

An MoU between ICAB and CIPFA, UK was signed on 28 January 2017. Under this MoU, an ICAB member can also become a members of CIPFA subject to fulfillment of certain criteria.

An ICAB Member with good standing having five or more years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible for Full Membership of CIPFA as Chartered Public Finance Accountant (CIPFA) and the members having fewer than five years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible as Affiliate member of CIPFA (CIPFA Affiliat).

ICAB members having CIPFA Affiliate membership, or having no working experience in public sector can gain CIPFA status with the successful completion of exams of only two papers i.e. Public Sector Financial Reporting and Strategic Public Finance.

Membership Pathways Agreement (MPA) with CPA Australia

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) has recently signed a Membership Pathways Agreement (MPA) with CPA Australia, one of the largest accounting bodies around the world. Through this agreement, ICAB members can be the members of CPA Australia just after passing 04 papers (i.e. 1. Ethics and Governance, 2. Financial Reporting, 3. Global Strategy & Leadership and 4. Strategic Management Accounting) out of their 12 papers. This MPA has been in effect since 20 July 2018.

Membership through Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ) International Pathway Program (IPP)

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) signed an MoU with the Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ). Under this, ICAB members living in Australia or New Zealand having five years post qualification experience at anywhere will be eligible to be member of CA ANZ after successful completion of CA ANZ International Pathway Program (IPP).

There will be no requirement of passing CA ANZ general route examinations by eligible ICAB members as their International Pathway Program (IPP) workshop through case studies would examine the contemporary Australasian business, accounting and finance environment relevant for members of ICAB. On the other hand, CA ANZ members can also be members of ICAB subject to having Bangladeshi citizenship and other requirements as prescribed by ICAB Bye-laws.

Membership of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC)

Efforts are underway for ICAB to Become a member of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC). This would create an opportunity for the members of ICAB to involve in the valuation process of local and foreign investment in Bangladesh.

This would allow Chartered Accountants to put up their highly essential services and play positive roles in attracting foreign investment. With regard to this, ICAB has already conducted a Members Conference. More so, a virtual meeting with the CEO of IVSC was held on 8 June 2021 where the IVSC proposed ICAB to become member of IVSC on pro-rata basis.

Other Memberships

ICAB is an active member of International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), Confederation of Asian and Pacific Accountants (CAPA) and South Asian Federation of Accountants (SAFA). ICAB is also an associate member of Chartered Accountants Worldwide (CAW).